

THE INDIRECT PROTECTION OF RAPISTS UNDER THE NIGERIAN LAW.

BY

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**BEING A LONG ESSAY/PROJECT PRESENTED TO THE FACULTY OF LAW,
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DECLARATION

I declare that the work in this long essay titled ‘THE INDIRECT PROTECTION OF RAPISTS UNDER THE NIGERIAN LAW’ has been researched by me in the Faculty of law, University of Nigeria, Enugu Campus. The information derived from the literature has been duly acknowledged in the text and a list of reference provided. The content of this work is original and has not been submitted in part or full for the award of any degree of this or any other institution.

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to every victim of sexual assault who cannot get the justice and healing they desire.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I wish to express my thankfulness to God for his direction and love throughout my years as a law student. His presence in my life helped me get through the ASUU strikes, the COVID stay-at-home era, and the IPOB sit-at-home that all disrupted my studies and brought me low numerous times. To my supervisor, Barr. Edwin Arum, I owe a great deal of respect and appreciation. Without his direction, feedback, and support, I could not have produced a better research paper.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

TITLE PAGE	I
DECLARATION PAGE	II
DEDICATION	III
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	IV
TABLE OF CONTENTS	V
TABLE OF CASES	VII
TABLE OF STATUTES	VIII
ABSTRACT	X

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of Study	1
1.2. Statement of the Problem	3
1.3. Research Questions	4
1.4. Aim and Objectives of the Study	4
1.5. Research Methodology	4
1.6 Scope of the Study	4
1.7. Literature Review	5

CHAPTER TWO: RAPE

2.1. The Criminalization of Rape: A Historical Perspective	8
2.2. Factors that Give Rise to the Crime	9
2.2.1. Cultural Factors	9
2.2.2. Biological Factors	11
2.2.3. Social Factors	12
2.2.4. Legal Factors	14

CHAPTER THREE: LEGAL AND SOCIETAL ATTITUDE TOWARDS RAPE

3.1. An in-depth analysis of the Nigerian Law on Rape	17
3.1.1. The Criminal Code Act	18
3.1.2. The Penal Code Act	20
3.1.3. The Violence Against Persons' Protection Act	22
3.2. The problems/inadequacies of the law on rape/Society's view	24

CHAPTER FOUR: THE RAPE VICTIM'S PERSPECTIVE

4.1. Introduction	30
4.2. An Appraisal of The Victim's Traditional Perspectives on Rape	31
4.3. A Critique of the Legal and Judicial Hurdles of Proving Rape: The Victim's Perspective	32
4.3.1. Carnal Knowledge or Penetration	33
4.3.2. Consent	35
4.3.3. Corroboration	38

4.3.4. Rape Culture and Hurdle of Stigmatization	41
4.3.5. Judicial Hurdles: Courtroom Observations of Judges Demeanors to victims	42
4.3.6. Administrative Hurdles: The Attitude of the Police	44
CHAPTER FIVE: FINDINGS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION	
5.1. Summary of findings	46
5.2. Observations	47
5.3. Recommendations	47
5.4. Contribution to Knowledge	50
5.5. Suggested Areas of Research	50
BIBLIOGRAPHY	51

TABLE OF CASES

Afor Lucky v State LPELR-40541 (SC)	7, 16
DPP v Morgan (1976) AC 182	21, 28, 38
Francis Okpanefe v State (1969) LCN/1643 SC	40, 43
IGP v Sunmonu (2021) LCN/4962 (SC)	29
Iko v State (2001) 7 S.C. (II) 115	17, 29, 37
Isaac Sambo v State (1993) LCN2527(SC)	41
Julius v State (2019) LPELR-48170 (CA)	36
Musa Natasha v State (2017) LPELR-42359(SC)	52
People v John Z (Cal.2003) 60 PP.183	37
Popoola v State (2018) LPELR-43853 (SC)	32
Ponu v State (2020) LCN/4948 (SC)	28
R v Russen (1777) 1 East PC 439	36
Santhosh Moolya and Surendra Gowda v State of India (2010) 5 SCC, India	43
Solomon Okayomon v State (1973) 1ALL NLR 16	21, 36, 41, 51

TABLE OF STATUTES

CHILD RIGHTS ACT, 2003	1, 10
Section 31	19
Section 32	39
CRIMINAL LAW OF LAGOS STATE, 2015	
Section 260	38
EVIDENCE ACT	27, 48
Section 180(g)	37
Section 200	29
Section 209	38
Section 211	38
KANO SHARIA PENAL CODE, 2000	
Section 127	30
NIGERIAN CRIMINAL CODE ACT, 2004	1, 8, 22
Section 6	21, 36, 39, 49
Section 7	19
Section 25	21
Section 30	30
Section 215	39
Section 216	49
Section 217	38, 49
Section 218	39, 49
Section 219	38, 49
Section 220	49
Section 221	38, 49
Section 222	39
Section 357	4, 15, 16, 17, 20, 34, 36.
Section 360	26
NIGERIAN PENAL CODE, 2004	1, 8, 19, 49
Section 39	22
Section 50	23
Section 55	27
Section 83	21
Section 281	22
Section 282	4, 15, 16, 34
Section 283	22

SEXUAL OFFENCES ACT OF GREAT BRITAIN, 2003	36
THE ADMINISTRATION OF CRIMINAL JUSTICE ACT	
Section 258	33
THE AFRICAN CHARTER ON HUMAN AND PEOPLE'S RIGHTS	1
THE INTERNATIONAL COVENANT ON CIVIL AND POLITICAL RIGHTS	1
THE UNITED NATIONS CONVENTION ON THE ELIMINATION OF ALL FORMS OF DISCRIMINATION AGAINST WOMEN(CEDAW)	1
VIOLENCE AGAINST PROHIBITION ACT, 2015	1, 10, 37
Section 1	23, 49
Section 3	34

ABSTRACT

Nigerian Society lays claim to the most severe intolerance of sexual immorality in all its forms, but some disputations have been made against these claims by critics who allege that its laws gives the lie to its vaunted claims especially regarding rape. This study seeks to engage in an assessment of the Nigerian Legal system as it pertains to rape in order to ascertain whether its provisions offer sufficient protection for victims of rape. This study does this by identifying the existing frameworks protecting rape in Nigeria, identifying the challenges surrounding the interpretation of rape laws and demonstrating how these laws offer protection for rapists in Nigeria. The study adopts the doctrinal research methodology which will be library-oriented. This study finds that although, Nigerian Laws have provisions intended to protect rape victims, these provisions are really ineffective at doing so because they have onerous conditions that victims find impossible to meet. As a result, the laws inadvertently give rapists protection. This study recommends modifications of legal requirements for the crime of rape, retraining police officers to properly handle its complaints, tougher penalties for rapists, and suggesting the establishment of special courts to properly deal with the crime.

CHAPTER ONE

1.1. Background of Study

Survivors of rape experience negative physical, psychological, and social impacts, and this has overtime grown to be a global public health issue.¹ The abnormal act is a major crime, which is in violation of the principles of any agreements, treaties, conventions, or laws pertaining to human rights and a raft of charters of which Nigeria is a signatory to; such as the African Charter on Human and People's Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, and the United Nations Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW).²

Rape has been defined as any form of sexual penetration which is often characterized by using force, threat, fear of harm or any other means to compromise someone's consent to indulge in sexual activity.³

Around the world, one in every five women has been the victim of rape or another type of sexual assault.⁴ Africa, the Middle East, and Southeast Asia, on the other hand, have the highest reported rates of rape in the world.⁵

The Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act of 2015, the Child Right Act of 2003, and the Nigerian Criminal and Penal Codes are among the legal provisions that forbid the act of rape in Nigeria. Despite the implementation of the aforementioned steps, rape continues to occur in Nigeria unabated.

Young adults are more vulnerable to being victims of rape, with young women being more vulnerable, according to relevant researches done on the subject matter.⁶ It has also been noticed that street vendors, out-of-school youths, in-school adolescents, university students, and women

¹ Sylvia Ifemeje and Emmanuel Obidimma, 'A Critique of Incessant Violations of Women's Health and Reproductive Rights in Nigeria', (2013) (11) *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization*; 1.

² Akintayo Ogunwale, Frederick Oshiname & Folakemi Ajagunna, 'A Review of the Conceptual Issues, Social Epidemiology, Prevention and Control Efforts Relating to Rape in Nigeria', (2019) (23) (4), *African Journal of Reproductive Health*.

³ Adekunbi Imosemi & Odusanya Adedamola, 'Rape in a Contemporary Nigeria: The Urgent Need for a Review of the Legal Responses' (2018) (6) (4), *International Journal of Business & Law Research*; 64.

⁴ Ibid, Sylvia Ifemeje and Emmanuel Obidimma.

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Mercy Ozoya & Mathew Egharevba, 'Taming the Rape Scourge in Nigeria: Issues and Actions' *ResearchGate* (2016). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320077852> accessed October 16, 2022.

whose ability to make mature sex-related decisions and/or consent has been damaged are among the groups of young people who are most affected.⁷ Rape victims, however, do not have an age restriction. Overtime, it has been seen that this crime affects both the young and old. In some cases, victims of the crime cut across gender. Nevertheless, reports have shown that the female gender is the worst hit. It is estimated that over 90% of rape victims in Nigeria are females.⁸

The act of rape violates the right of women to self-preservation, violates their privacy, it is inhumane and brutal to the strength of their psyche. Rape victims frequently experience shame, humiliation, and fear, and there is often little to not legal protection for them. Even the law enforcement officials tasked with keeping these victims safe are seen to also engage in the act of harassing them in very horrifying ways; sometimes even subject them to further sexual harassment. For instance, one report carried the story of a police officer in Abuja who had sexually assaulted a fourteen-year old who had come to the police station to report a case of fighting.⁹ Because she threatened to report the policeman's inappropriate advances to her, he sexually assaulted her viciously. These examples, as well as many others, abound in the daily existence of females in Nigeria.

Rape victims in Nigeria frequently experience humiliating treatment, prejudice, and social stigmatization, rather than social assistance and care. Many rape survivors would rather not speak up because of these negative societal repercussions. This condition has the potential to provide a significant obstacle to preventative and control measures.

The issue of rape permeates the entirety of the world. It is an issue that has continually put women at risk all over the world. One of the most severe types of gender-based violence against women in various regions of the world is rape, along with other sexually violent acts. According to a survey from the World Health Organisation (W.H.O), one-fifth of all women have been victims of rape and other similar sexually assaults.¹⁰ Rape and other sexually violent behaviours disproportionately affect women.

⁷ Ibid, Mercy Ozoya & Mathew Egharevba.

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Caroline Muoghalu, 'Rape and Women's Sexual Health in Nigeria: The Stark Realities of Being Female in a Patriarchal World' (2012) (19) (1-2), *The African Anthropologist*; 35.

¹⁰ Akintayo Ogunwale & Rotimi Afolabi, 'Prevalence, Determinants and Coercive Strategies Relating to Marital Rape Amongst Women in Oyo State, Nigeria' (2022) (56) (2), *Ghana Medical Journal*; 117.

Rape is not only circumscribed to single people. It has been found that couples are also victims of a brand of rape that has been termed marital rape. Marital rape is a scourge that brings most marital couples to their knees psychologically and emotionally. It is a problem in both developed and underdeveloped nations. Even though any partner in a marriage can become a victim of marital rape, like most rape cases, it primarily affects women. Research has been found that 10-14% of married women experience marital rape, which makes up around 25% of all rape cases. Research have also found that marital rape affects may women in Nigeria at a grander scale that is more than imagined.¹¹ For instance, a research done in the Nigerian state of Imo revealed that 14.2% of pregnant women in the state were subjected to forceful penetration by their husbands.¹²

Marital rape also has severe detrimental impact on families, society, and the physical, emotional, and mental health of the victims. It is possible that many marital rape survivors may endure other rap incidents. Unfortunately, compared to rape victims of other types, survivors of marital rape are less likely to receive assistance or support from friends, family, crisis centres, or the police. Lack of support in Nigeria may be attributed to the idea that rape does not fit into the sociocultural definition of sexual activity performed by one's spouse while under pressure.

While it is seen that rape is a terror especially to the female gender, it has also been observed that rape victims especially in Nigeria are subject to obnoxious cultural precepts and laws on rape that leave them unprotected, ashamed of their rape experience, litter them with doubts and fear, and ultimately embolden rapists to commit more crimes due to their knowledge that the sociocultural disposition of Nigeria will always protect them.

This study seeks to show how the sociocultural precepts and relevant laws of Nigeria ultimately ensures the protection of rapists in the country.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

The main problem that this study seeks to address is the legal and cultural hurdles that rape victims in Nigeria are directly and indirectly subjected to. These hurdles if not adequately addressed will only fan the embers of rape in Nigeria, embolden rapists and silence victims of rape in the country. It will ultimately banish these victims of rape to the gallows of their self-pity, mental disturbance,

¹¹ Ibid, Akintayo Ogunwale & Rotimi Afolabi.

¹² Ibid.

shame and public ridicule. Hence, this research is necessitated to provide an in-depth analysis of how sociocultural dispositions and legal tools indirectly provide protection for rapists in Nigeria.

Research Questions

In light of the foregoing problems, the research seeks to address the following research questions:

1. What are the existing legal frameworks prohibiting rape in Nigeria?
2. What are the challenges surrounding the interpretation of these laws?
3. How do these laws and sociocultural precepts provide protection for rapists in Nigeria?
4. What roles can the government and other relevant bodies play in dismantling the protection of rapists in Nigeria?

1.3.Aims and Objectives of the Research

The aim of this research is to provide an in-depth and extensive analysis on the indirect protection of rapists under the Nigerian law. While the objectives of the research are:

1. To identify the existing legal frameworks prohibiting rape in Nigeria.
2. To identify the challenges surrounding the interpretation of these laws.
3. To show how these laws and sociocultural precepts provide protection for rapists in Nigeria.
4. To show the roles that the government and other relevant bodies can play in dismantling the protection of rapists in Nigeria.

1.4.Research Methodology

The research methodology employed in this research is the doctrinal research methodology. This research relies on primary and secondary sources of law. The primary sources of law relied on the research include local legislations on rape and the decision of case laws bordering on rape in Nigerian courts. The secondary sources include, theses, legal journals, newspaper reports, blog and social media reports, and other academic papers sourced from both physical libraries and authentic internet portals.

1.5.Scope of the Study

This research examines the protection of rapists under Nigerian laws. Therefore, the study is limited only to legal frameworks that were in existence at the time of writing this research.

However, slight reference is made to foreign statutory frameworks at relevant points in the research.

1.6.Literature Review

Ozoya et al.,¹³ gives a clear picture of the numerical prevalence of rape all over the globe. Through their statistics on rape, it is seen that women are genuinely endangered by the cooing of rapists by the justice system and sociocultural dispositions. According to them, the United Kingdom (U.K) reports a rough total of 147,000 rape cases each year, but only about 1,000 of them result in convictions. The tendency is the same in India, where rape crimes are recorded every twenty minutes, but fewer than 25% of these instances result in prosecution. Furthermore, they state that only 18% of the rape that took place between 2001 and 2005 was reported in Lagos state, western Nigeria, while there were around 10,079 of such incidents in the state alone. Further writing on the subject matter, they emphasize that the police noted an increase in rape cases and determined that gang rape was the most prevalent because it topped the crime chart.

However, while it is settled that the prevalence of rape in Nigeria is a scourge to the female folks in the country, it is seen that the law which is supposed to be an instrument of protection has done little to protect rape victims in the country. Ashiru and Orifowomo¹⁴ reiterate this viewpoint. They state that the Nigerian law's current rape-related laws are insufficient and antiquated; hence, they must be updated to reflect the variety of scenarios in modern society that may qualify as rape. They specifically emphasize on the position of most Nigerian laws on the gender relation of rape to only the females. They maintain that men and boys too can be raped and as such must be factored in by the law in the definition of what constitutes rape.

Daru et al.¹⁵, conducted a pedantic study on the issue of rape and the specific targeting of young females by perpetrators of the crime. According to them, young people, especially young females are the major victims of this crime. This is because they are particularly vulnerable to sexual coercion (force) and violence that are utilized by perpetrators of rape as tools for the commission of rape. They posit that this coercion clearly involves the use of force; however, other times, it is

¹³ Ibid, Mercy Ozoya & Mathew Egharevba.

¹⁴ Mo Ashiru & Oluwaseun Orifowomo, 'Law of Rape in Nigeria and England: Need to Re-Invent in the Twenty-First Century' (2015) (38), *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization*; 32.

¹⁵ Patrick Daru, Enahire Osagie & Ors, 'Analysis of Cases of Rape As Seen at the Jos University Teaching Hospital, Jos, North-Central, Nigeria' (2011) (14) (1), *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice*; 48.

more subtle and involves economic and psychological manipulation. Furthermore, in the study conducted by Daru et al., they find that girls under the age of sixteen years are at the greater risk of being sexually harassed and raped, accounting for about 63.8% of the total cases of rape seen in their study.

However, it is seen that while there are laws that prohibit rape in Nigeria, its framework and provisions are in divergence to international laws and instruments on human rights. This is seen especially in the burden of proof attached to proving rape in Nigerian courts. In critiquing Nigerian laws on rape, Love Ayodele¹⁶ states that human rights standard should be given primary consideration when applying the law to evidence adduced at trials. According to her, the Nigerian legal system, like many other justice system globally, demands that the prosecution prove the defendant's guilt beyond reasonable doubt. The prosecutor is mandated to do this by introducing compelling evidence to each support each element of the crime. All the elements of the crime must be derived from the derived from the relevant statute's definition of the offence; otherwise, the accused will not be found guilty. According to Love Ayodele, the elements of proving offence in rape cases are assiduous tasks that most times prove very difficult for rape victims to surmount. Such almost impervious tasks are seen in the decision of the Supreme Court in *Afor Lucky v. State*¹⁷, on the elements of proving rape. According to the Supreme Court, the elements include:

- a. That there was a penetration;
- b. That the act of sexual intercourse was done without the consent of the prosecutrix or that the consent (if any) was obtained by fraud, force, threat, intimidation, deceit or impersonation;
- c. That the prosecutrix was not the wife of the accused; and
- d. That the accused had the mens rea, that is the intention to have sexual intercourse with the prosecutrix without her consent or that the accused acted recklessly not caring whether the prosecutrix consented or not.

¹⁶ Love Ayodele, *Through the Cases: Development in the Law of Rape in Nigeria and Its Consistency with International Human Rights Law* (Theses).

¹⁷ (2016) LPELR-40541 (SC)

According to Love Ayodele, the burden of proving these elements can be painfully excruciating for the victim of rape. It is also seen in those elements of proving rape that the Supreme Court endorsed marital rape by excusing forceful penetration of wives by their husbands.

To combat the scourge and incidence of rape in Nigeria, there should be holistic efforts that cuts across the breadth of the society. This is also the view of Emmanuel et al.¹⁸, in a study conducted by them on the unchecked prevalence of rape in the Nigerian society. According to them, to tame the spread of rape in the country, solutions targeted at curbing the crime must be all-encompassing. They maintain that there should be collective efforts by survivors of the crime, religious organizations, legislators, law enforcement agents and bodies, and civil society in developing a robust body of law that is tailored towards suppressing the protection of rapists in the country. According to Emmanuel et al., these collective efforts ought to develop creative, ethical, and situational recommendations for victim rehabilitation and the punishment of rapists. Furthermore, they reiterate that Nigeria ought to adopt and put into practice the African Charter on Human and People's Rights or the Rights of Women in Africa Protocol.

However, there is need for a broader research effort on this subject matter. This research seeks to fill the major gaps that is seen on the issue of rape in Nigeria, by building on existing literatures on the issue as an attempt to tackle the levity of rape incidence in the country.

¹⁸ Emmanuel Akinade, Temitayo Adewuyi & Afolashade Sulaiman, 'Socio-legal Factors that Influence the Perpetuation of Rape in Nigeria' (2010) (5), *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*; 1763.

CHAPTER TWO

HISTORICAL AND CONCEPTUAL ANALYSIS OF RAPE

2.1. The Criminalization of Rape: A Historical Perspective

Rape is as old as the creation of man. As far as back as the Bible was being written, incidences of rape were already being recorded. Throughout the anecdotes and stories that inundated the Bible, the stories of rape formed part of the sins that the Bible prohibited. Rape during biblical times had no bearing of social fury on the perpetrator of the act, but on the family of the victim.

However, the Hebrew Laws, set forth in the first five books of the Bible, provided criminal penalties for rape.¹⁹ The earliest written laws designating rape as a crime were promulgated in the Code of Hammurabi around the beginning of 17th Century B.C.²⁰ The earliest English Common law consisted of written promulgations of Kings, beginning with Aethelbert of Kent, who reigned in 597 A.D.²¹ His laws and those of other Kings did not often specifically state an act as a crime or civil offense but indicated the penalty or compensation.

Later, the English Common law defined rape as the unlawful carnal knowledge of a female over ten years of age by a man who is not her husband, through coercion or against the woman's will.²² Except for the change in the age of consent to a more realistic level, this definition has generally been followed with a few minor variations.

The history of criminalizing rape in Nigeria stems from the nation's enactment of the Criminal and Penal Codes. Both legislations formally prohibited rape in the nation through various provisions. While the Criminal Code applies to the southern part of Nigeria, the northern part of the country is subject to the Pena Code. However, overtime, it was seen that the provisions of these laws on rape were not adequate and failed to cater for the modern realities and patterns of rape in Nigeria. Hence, the need for a review and change of laws. In response to this, the Federal Government established the Committee on the Review of Discriminatory Laws Against Women in August, 2005.²³ This Committee, which operated under the National Human Rights Commission's

¹⁹ Chris Smith, 'History of Rape and Rape Laws', (1974) (60) (4) *Women Lawyers Journal*; 1.
<<https://www.ojp.gov/ncjrs/virtual-library/abstracts/history-rape-and-rape-laws>> accessed October 20, 2022.

²⁰ Ibid.

²¹ Ibid.

²² Ibid.

²³ Omolola Akinwole, 'A Review of Literature: Rape and Communication Media Strategies in Nigeria' (*A Theses*).

umbrella, was tasked with reviewing discriminatory laws, including those pertaining to rape. On May 16, 2006, the Committee delivered its final report to the then Federal Minister of Justice.²⁴ Additionally, responding to the growing incidence of rape in various states of the federation, certain states enacted Child Rights Act that were geared towards combating all forms of child abuse, including rape. However, these state Acts have also grown to be inadequate to the shape that rape in the country has taken. To combat this shape, there were agitations from non-governmental organizations (NGOs) focused on rape and gender issues, survivors of rape and well-meaning Nigerians for a robust legal framework that factored in the current realities of rape patterns in the country. These agitations gave rise to the enactment of the Violence Against Persons Prohibition (VAPP) Act²⁵, which is more in-depth and holistic in its punitive measures against rape and other issues relating to the crime.

2.2.Factors that Give Rise to Rape

There are contributing factors that give rise to rape. These factors will be calibrated under the following categories in this chapter:

- a. Cultural factors;
- b. Biological factors;
- c. Legal factors; and
- d. Social factors.

2.2.1. Cultural Factors

The acceptance of sexual assault and rape is influenced by cultural values such as male honour, masculinity, and men's sexual entitlement in many different ways. Rape occurs more frequently in areas where there is a strong male superiority ideology that emphasizes power, physical strength, and male honour.²⁶ In many cultures, women, as well as men, perceive marriage as entailing the obligation on women to be sexually accessible nearly without limit. This thinking justifies rape even in marriages. In such cultures, women may have very few acceptable choices to resist sexual advances even outside of marriage.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act, 2015.

²⁶ The Advocates for Human Rights, 'Sexual Assault and Cultural Norms' *The Advocate for Human Rights Blog* (2006) <https://www.stopvaw.org/sexual_assault_and_cultural_norms> accessed October 20, 2022.

According to the underlying theory of rape as a learned behaviour, “social conditions, such as cultural norms, rules, and prevailing attitudes about sex, mould and structure the behaviour of the rapists within the context of the larger social system, fostering rape-prone environments and, in effect, teaching men to rape.”²⁷

For instance, a study found that male dominance, a larger societal patterns of violence, and ideologies that support male aggression – especially when that aggression is sexually directed – all correlate with sexual violence (such as low levels of female political and economic empowerment and high levels of sexual separation).²⁸

Furthermore, as men shift their aggressiveness toward women, they may no longer be able to be controlled patriarchally or supported economically due to the confluence of cultural norms that promote male supremacy.

Also, a subculture that condones sexual violence can be created when cultural norms that devalue women meet with norms that promote male aggression and authority. For instance, a recent study on sexual assault at the United States (U.S.) Air Force Academy discovered that nearly 12% of the female graduates in 2003 had experienced rape or an attempted rape while they were students there. The problem of rape, according to female experiences who spoke up about their experiences, is “widespread and the result of a culture that is hostile to women.”²⁹

Additionally, it is seen that cultures that experience high levels of violence and conflict are linked to an increase in sexual assault. This is reiterated by the World Health Organization (W.H.O), where it reported that “countries with a culture of violence, or where violent conflict is taking place, experience a surge in practically all forms of violence, including sexual violence.”³⁰

Similar findings have been made by other researchers who discovered a strong connection between sexual assault rates and social disorder, or the existence of circumstances that undermine conventional societal institutions like the church or family networks.³¹

²⁷ Owen Jones, ‘Sex, Culture, and the Biology of Rape: Toward Explanation and Prevention’ (2004) (87) (4) *California Law Review*.

²⁸ Peggy Sanday, ‘The Socio-Cultural Context of Rape: A Cross-Cultural Study’ (1981) (37) (4) *Journal of Social Issues*; 5-27.

²⁹ *Ibid*, The Advocates of Human Rights.

³⁰ *Ibid*.

³¹ *Ibid*, The Advocates for Human Rights.

Also, the cultural tenets of Nigeria surrounding marriage is a major enabler of rape. The commodification of women in African and Nigerian marriages as part of marital customs embolden men to see their wives as objects of satisfaction which they can access anytime they choose to. In most cultural norms in Nigeria, women are regarded as the below their husbands and must endure the sexual anomalies of these husbands regardless of the consequences. These fundamental concepts in Nigerian marriages fuel the beastly animations of most men as to their sexual relationships with women, thus increasing the incidence of rape in the Nigerian and African society.

Biological Factors

Biological factors causing the rise of rape has been explained through the biological theories of sexual assault. These theories contend that although there is “gene” that specifically leads men to commit rape, there may be a tendency to rape, there may be a tendency to rape as a result of evolution.³² According to this hypothesis, rape-prone men may have greater reproductive success (such as a higher number of offspring).³³ This reproductive advantage leads to a widespread male propensity for rape over an extended period of time.

Other scholars contend that the propensity for rape is a result of reproductive adaptations rather than an adaptation in and of itself, such as the pursuit of multiple partners.³⁴

Biological explanations of the behaviour of a victim of sexual assault have been paired with these biological explanations of the perpetrator’s behaviour. Women have evolved to resist rape because they prefer having sex with a small number of partners.³⁵ Furthermore, these theories contend that sexual assault-related “trauma” was a successful reproductive response since it prevented subsequent rape for the women who experienced it.³⁶

Although some proponents of biological theory contend that identifying a biological foundation for rape does not absolve it, such theories can support and sustain ideas that absolve offenders from responsibility for their conduct and blame the victims. For instance, some proponents of

³² The Advocates for Human Rights, ‘Biological Theories of Sexual Assault’ *The Advocates for Human Rights* (2006) <https://www.stopvaw.org/biological_theories_of_sexual_assault> accessed October 20, 2022.

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Ibid, Owen Jones.

³⁵ Ibid, The Advocates for Human Rights.

³⁶ Ibid.

biological theories contend that women should refrain from clothing provocatively because men cannot control their urges to rape. This point of view contends that women who are raped must have created the conditions that led to the rape, and the best course of action is to educate them on how to avoid being victims of rape.

Biological justifications for rape also have a tendency to “naturalize” the offender’s behaviour, suggesting that it is “acceptable” and possibly unchangeable. Additionally, these ideas minimize the victim’s anguish and suffering. Furthermore, biological theories have a big impact on how the criminal justice system handles rape. If rape is a biological adaptation, then there should be financial sanction as well as chemical castration or hormonal therapies, which can be considered human rights breaches in and of themselves. Furthermore, biological theories are insufficient as an explanation for why males rape women who are sterile or their intimate partners and spouses.

Additionally, the physiological superiority of men also gives them undue advantage to overpower women. This biological difference in both genders can be said to be a major causative factor in the spike of rape cases. Due to the fact that rapists need to employ force to overpower their victims, the physiology of men unduly gives male rapists a violent advantage over their prey.

2.2.2. Social Factors

There is a raft of categorized factors that contribute to rape especially in Nigeria. These factors will be dealt sequentially under this subheading. They include:

a. Under-Reportage of Rape Cases:

One of the most heinous crimes that is least frequently reported in Nigeria and other countries is rape. The problem is exacerbated by the dearth of trustworthy rape statistics when we attempt to understand the scope of its prevalence. The fact that the majority of rape victims simply refuse to come forward and disclose instances of sexual abuse to the police presents a significant challenge when addressing this issue. A sense of shame, remorse, or self-blame regarding their participation in the rape assaults may be sufficient for many rape victims to keep them from going forward and filing charges. In many cases, the public appears to be more willing to hold the assault victim accountable than the rapist.

Rape continues to be one of the most underreported crimes because of a number of obstacles that stop sexual assault victims from reporting their experiences. For instance, a little girl named

“Folake” was imprisoned after accusing a man of rape.³⁷ She claimed to be a domestic worker and claimed that the husband of her employer had dragged her into his bedroom, made her watch a pornographic movie, and then forced her to have sex. Her claim was verified by a medical examination. However, she was the one who was brought to court, accused of defamation for making the claim, and subsequently remanded in jail.

Furthermore, social stigma attached to the victim, the scare of being ostracized by the rest of the society, and the reticence of the police to effectively prosecute the rape case are also part of the fundamental reasons why most rape crimes are not reported.

b. Poverty and Economic Factor

In Nigeria, poverty is a serious issue that affects many households. Many families in the country have been pushed by poverty and the economic downturn to enable their female children and teenagers to engage in hawking wares and goods, even during inappropriate times of the day and dangerous locations filled with street urchins that are bereft of the slightest respect to the body rights of women. They are pushed into these dangerous situations for the mere fact of feeding their families.

c. The confluence of rape and stigmatization

In Nigeria, women are commonly the victim of two crimes. First, the abuse she is subjected and the failure of governmental institutions to afford them adequate protection from their abusers. Therefore, due to the structural defects in protecting women, there seems to be a resignation to fate; a tacit endorsement of silence of rape victims. This culture of silence fosters the reign of stigmatizing rape victims in the country.

Because of the widespread social stigma attached to rape, female victims in Nigeria are compelled to keep their rape attacks a secret in order to avoid shame and public humiliation. Even the victim’s parents frequently find it difficult to denounce such situations in public. It is seen that when a woman is raped in Nigeria and the incident is made, the victim and her family are ostracized by other members of the community. This culture only succeeds in giving steam to the rapists. They

³⁷ Amnesty International for the Public Hearing on the Domestic Violence and Related Matters Bill, at the Lagos State House of Assembly, April 12, 2006.

feast on the culture of silence that is being propagated; after all, not a word would be said following the rape incident, not even to the police.

Most times in the Nigerian setting, it is seen that the perpetrators of this crime are relatives and acquaintances of the victims. In such cases, the prevalent culture in Nigeria is to treat such matter secretively so as not to incur the wrath of the extended family or even for the mere fact that the familial relationship with the family of perpetrator is kept intact and not ruffled by the matter. As such, the perpetrator goes scot-free and unscathed.

2.2.3. Legal Factors

The disposition of Nigeria's justice system towards is pitiable and despicable and deserves. This is seen from the court's body-language to the crime, to the tedious burden of proof attached to proving rape which dissuades rape victims from reporting their rape incidents and the inadequacy of Nigerian legislations on the modern patterns of rape. Hence, these legal factors fuelling the rise of rape in Nigeria will be reviewed under this chapter. They include:

i. The complicity of the Nigerian legislations on the issue of rape:

Government authorities in Nigeria, both at the federal and state levels, have not appropriately addressed gender-based violence, especially rape. The legislations of the nation on issues of rape appear to play a role in some of the country's rising rape rates. For instance, it is highly likely that the application of Section 357 of the Criminal Code Act,³⁸ which states that:

“Any person who has unlawful carnal knowledge of a woman or girl, without her consent, or with her consent, if the consent is obtained by force or by means of false threats or intimidation of any kind, or by fear of harm, or by means of false threats or fraudulent representation as to the nature of the act, or in the case of a married woman, by impersonating her husband, is guilty of an offence called rape.”

Also, Section 282 of the Penal Code³⁹ which provides that:

“Sexual intercourse by a man with his own wife is not rape, if she has attained puberty.”

³⁸ CAP 77, LFN, 1990.

³⁹ CAP 53, LFN, 2004.

A pedantic review of the aforementioned provisions seem to excuse child and marital rape. These deductions is reached especially when one sees that Section 357 of the Criminal Code Act does not provide marital rape; rape according to this legal provision is only prohibited where a person “impersonates” the husband of the victim. Hence, if forceful penetration is carried out by the husband himself, it is not recognised as rape under the Criminal Code.

Section 282 of the Penal Code also adopts almost the same view of exonerating perpetrators of marital rape. According to that provision as seen above, a man cannot rape his wife, especially if such wife has reached the age of puberty. This provision by its stance endorses two heinous crime that is worth noting; first, marital rape and child marriage. Such laws are in violation to international instruments on human rights, are seen to be cover for marital rape and child abuse and also emboldens perpetrators of rape especially amongst married couples.

Furthermore, the Supreme Court in the case of *Afor Lucky v. State*⁴⁰, decided that a man cannot rape his wife. The result of this decision is the tacit legalization of marital rape by the Supreme Court for the mere reason that the rapists are married men.

ii. Indifference in the handling of rape cases

The criminal justice system in Nigeria is also fraught with structural defects that protect and embolden rapists in the nation. For instance, it is well known that most personnel of the Nigeria Police Force (NPF) gleefully treat rape victims as though they are the actual culprits. In certain instances, it is said that the police accuse the victims of motivating the attacker’s sexual advances by faulting their location, outfits and the victim’s relationship with the rapist.

iii. Strict Burden of Proof

Most times, the burden of proof in a rape case can be unusually strict. This has led to the exoneration of culprits even when the evidence is overwhelming and reasonably convincing. It is reported that “over a hundred cases of sexual violence against women and children often go without the culprits being prosecuted or jailed.”⁴¹ This is mostly because of the burden of proof placed on the victims. While this is excused on the altar of not jailing an innocent, it has been stretched thin to the detriment of actual rape victims. For instance, there was a case of a man who

⁴⁰ (2016) LPELR-40541 (SC)

⁴¹ Alhassan Abubakar, ‘Child Rape: Who Speaks for the Victims?’ *Hope for Nigeria Online* (2013) <<https://www.hopefornigeriaonline.com/rape-who-speaks-for-the-victims>> accessed October 20, 2022.

sexually assaulted a six year old girl in 1999.⁴² In a twist of event, the magistrate discharged the accused for want of “corroboration” by the prosecutor. This was regardless of the blood stained underwear of the victim; the testimony of the mother who bore witness to the vaginal pain of the child while she bathe her that same day and a medical evidence from a government licensed hospital.⁴³

Section 357 of the Criminal Code further complicates the issue of proving rape in a Nigerian law court. The section states thus:

“Any person who has unlawful carnal knowledge of a woman or girl, without her consent, or with her consent, if the consent is obtained by force or by any means of threats or intimidation of any kid, or by fear of harm, or by means of false and fraudulent representation as to the nature of the act, or in the case of a married woman, by personating her husband, is guilty of an offence which is called rape.”

This section of the Criminal Code consolidates the court’s position of marital rape in Nigeria; that is, that a married woman cannot be raped by her husband as far as the Nigerian jurisprudence on rape is concerned. This position of the court was reiterated in *Iko v. State*.⁴⁴ It was further held in that case that there must be a corroborating evidence as to forceful penetration of the victim. This means that asides from the testimony of the victim that he/she was forcefully penetrated, a third party must corroborate this testimony as true. The issue of corroboration is a particularly herculean task in proving rape as most rape cases happen behind closed doors or in isolated locations that are scarce of human movement.

These factors only succeed in embolden and excusing the rapists regardless of the overwhelming evidence against them.

⁴² Ibid.

⁴³ Ibid.

⁴⁴ (2001) 7 S.C. (II) 115.

CHAPTER THREE

LEGAL AND SOCIETAL ATTITUDE TOWARDS RAPE

Since rape has exposed its ugly face in every community, it is not a hypothetical problem. But how can we characterize the brutality of this despicable hoax in Africa, particularly in Nigeria? What are the characteristics of our societies that makes women particularly susceptible to abuse of all kinds? What could have prompted the offenders to violate their victims sexually? Inadequate national legislation in nations that do not update its rape laws is another reason why victims of rape are discouraged from filing a lawsuit because they know that there is a high likelihood that the accused will not be found guilty of the crime.⁴⁵

In Nigeria, rape is a common criminal sexual behavior that not only violates the dignity of victims but also jeopardizes their health and wellness. The causes of rape include elements linked to unfavorable social, cultural, and economic circumstances.⁴⁶

The majority of rape incidents go unreported for a variety of reasons, including the victim's stigma in society, their fear of rejection by their family and community, and the police's possible reluctance to file an official complaint due to a lack of sufficient evidence.⁴⁷ Even if the incident is reported and the perpetrator is found not guilty after a trial, the victim is made to feel degraded and stigmatized.⁴⁸

3.1 An in-depth analysis of the Nigerian Law on Rape.

Given the prevalence of rape in Nigeria, the crime is regarded as the worst nightmare a woman or girl may experience because it frequently results in stigmatization and social confusion for many. Many nations, like England and the United States of America, have updated their rape laws to reflect the widespread sexual abuse and other forms of immorality that have become common in

⁴⁵ Otitodiri O. An appraisal of the Offence of Rape in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Legal Studies*, 2014: 11:60-71.

⁴⁶ Olaleye OS and Ajuwon AJ. Experience of non-consensual sex among students in a tertiary institution in Ibadan, Nigeria. *Sierra Leone Journal of Biomedical Research*, 2011, 3: 175-183

⁴⁷ The British Crime Survey Interpersonal Violence Module 2005-2006 found that 40% of adults who are raped tell no one about it; that 31% who are sexually abused reach adulthood without having disclosed their childhood sexual abuse. They conclude that this means that victims do not get the support they need to deal with the sexual abuse or violence they have experienced; that where victims do try and access support, it has not always been available. www.crimereduction.homeoffice.gov.uk/sexualoffences/sexual04.htm accessed 02 November 2022

⁴⁸ 3. Eze UO. *Prevention of Sexual Assault in Nigeria*. *Annals of Ibadan Post graduate Medicine*; 2013, 11 (2) 65- 70

the twenty-first century.⁴⁹ However, because the rules are strict and do not consider societal developments, Nigeria's rape laws need to be revisited. Rape has a catastrophic impact on its victims, their families, and society at large; those who have been raped often experience severe physical and psychological issues for years after the assault and may even be permanently scarred. Serious injuries, HIV infections, unintended pregnancies, etc. are examples of this.⁵⁰

Both statutes and Sharia Legislation serve as the foundation for Nigerian rape law. Depending on where in the nation the law is being enforced, certain parts of the rape laws are applied differently. The Criminal Code Act would be utilized if it were to be applied in the Southern States of the nation, as opposed to the Northern States of Nigeria, where the Penal Code Act is utilized.⁵¹ There haven't been any changes made to either the Criminal Code Act or the Penal Code Act in Nigeria since they were put into effect. Sharia law is also present and is in effect in the Northern States of Nigeria. It was recently reintroduced to these States.

The state of Zamfara, whose Sharia's Penal Code went into force on January 27, 2000, was the first to benefit from this legislation. Soon after, eleven more Northern States imitated it by introducing different Sharia laws.⁵²

The main defense of Sharia was that Nigerian law, which is founded on received English law and Christianity in its history and context, is insufficient to regulate the life of the typical Muslim there.

3.1.1 The Criminal Code Act

The criminal and penal codes in Nigeria both define rape. The Criminal Code's definition of rape in Section 357 is as follows:

⁴⁹ Akinwale Ashiru and Magaret Orifowomo „Law of Rape in Nigeria and England: NEED TO Re-invent in the Twenty-First Century“ *Journal of Law, policy and Globalization*, (2015), volume 38 page 28-38 <http://www.iiste.org/journals/index.php/JLPG/article/viewFile/23513/24235> accessed 02 November 2022

⁵⁰ Aliyu Ahmad, „The Crime of Rape in Nigeria: Inadequacies of Protection Mechanism“ *Umaru Musa Yar'adua University Law Journal*, (2014), volume 1, Number 1

⁵¹ The Criminal Code Act was in force in Northern Nigeria until 30 September 1960 and was replaced by the Penal Code Act on the 1 October 1960. The Penal Code Act is a prototype of the Indian Penal Code.

⁵² Comparison can be made as to what happens under Islamic law with regard to a divorced woman. Her former husband can take her into bed during the waiting period, known as idda

*"Unlawful carnal knowledge of a woman or girl without her consent, if obtained by force, menace or intimidation of any kind, fear or damage, or false and fraudulent representation as to the nature of the act, or in the case of a married woman, by impersonating her husband."*⁵³

The penis only needs to partially enter the vagina to be effective. It's not essential for there to have been an ejaculation or for the hymen to have been broken. The Code does not acknowledge that rape may involve other features, such as invasion of a woman or girl's anus or mouth, which could be just as traumatizing as penetration of the vagina. As far as the language of the Code suggests, only a woman or girl may be raped. Even though males have claimed to have been raped in recent years, the Criminal Code Act does not recognize this reality. Transsexuals are not included by the Criminal Code Act either.

A male under the age of 12 is deemed incapable of demonstrating carnal knowledge.⁵⁴ This is an unassailable presumption, therefore even if it can be demonstrated that he has entered puberty despite his age, he cannot be found guilty of the crime of rape or attempted rape. However, he might be found guilty of indecent assault.

A woman would not be physically capable of committing the act because vaginal penetration is necessary, which she is incapable of doing, but she may be guilty of counseling or aiding rape. A woman may not be physically capable of committing rape against a male or another woman, according to Ijalaiye⁵⁵, yet she may nevertheless be accused of the crime and convicted guilty of it.

Therefore, if a woman is detected in such a circumstance acting in violation of any of the provisions of section 7, whether one considers her to be a principle in the first or second degree, or an accessory before the fact, she would be considered to be a principal perpetrator of the crime of rape. There is still the legal presumption that a woman grants her husband her unconditional agreement to engage in sexual activity upon marriage. A husband cannot be charged with raping

⁵³ The Criminal Code, Section 357.

⁵⁴ section 30 of the Criminal Code Act

⁵⁵ Ijalaiye, D A "Sexual Offences in Nigeria" *Nigerian Interfaculty Law Journal*, 1 June 1991; (1991) Vol. II [N.I.L.J.]

his wife since section 6 of the Criminal Code Act also defines unlawful carnal knowledge as "carnal connection which takes place other than between a husband and wife"⁵⁶.

The mental element necessary for a charge of rape is the purpose to engage in sexual activity with a woman either without her consent or with disregard for whether she gave consent. Unfortunately, the ruling in *D.P.P v. Morgan*⁵⁷ is still a valid legal precedent under the Criminal Code Act. According to section 25 of the Criminal Code Act, the burden of proving an honest and reasonable mistake of fact does not fall on the accused who claims he believed the woman was consenting.⁵⁸

As a result, the prosecution must not only establish the actus reus (i.e., sexual contact without the woman's consent) and the mens rea (i.e., intent to engage in sexual contact with a girl or woman without her consent), but also establish that the accused had the intention to engage in sexual contact without the woman's consent. Even when it is clear that the accused committed the crime, the few examples that have actually reached the courts demonstrate how challenging it is to prove rape.⁵⁹

3.1.2 The Penal Code Act

On the other hand, Section 281 (1) of the Penal Code (which is operational in the Northern States provides thus:

“A man is said to commit rape who has sexual intercourse with a woman in any of the following circumstances- (a) against her will (b) without her consent (c) with her consent, when her consent

⁵⁶ The reference to ‘husband and wife’ under section 6 of the Criminal Code Act is not restricted to parties to a Christian marriage. Thus, such an act may also occur between parties who have conducted a valid marriage under another system, such as a customary law marriage.

⁵⁷ [1976] AC 182.

⁵⁸ Section 25 of the Criminal Code Act which deals with mistake of fact provides that: “a person who does or omits to do an act under an honest and reasonable but mistaken belief in the existence of any state of things is not criminally responsible for the act or omission to any greater extent than if the real state of things had been such as he believed to exist. The operations of this rule may be excluded by the express or implied provisions of the law relating to the subject.”

⁵⁹ The *Solomon Okoyomon v. State* case (1973) 1 ALL NLR 16. In this instance, the prosecutrix, an 11 to 12-year-old girl, claimed that the accused sexually assaulted her when she was out to get firewood. Evidence suggested that she had a venereal condition and that her hymen had been torn. No documentation was offered to show how long or by whom the defendant's hymen had been ruptured or that she had a venereal disorder similar to the one identified in the prosecutor's vagina. The prosecution was found to have failed to prove penetration as needed by the Criminal Code on appeal to the Supreme Court, and the appropriate offense was determined to have been committed was attempted rape and not rape

has been obtained by putting her in fear of death or of hurt (d) with her consent, when the man knows that he is not her husband and that her consent is given because she believes that he is another man to whom she is or believes herself to be lawfully married (e) with or without her consent when she is under fourteen years of age or of unsound mind”

The Penal Code Act prohibits women from committing the crime of rape, but the prosecution may still accuse them of aiding and abetting rape in accordance with section 83 of the Code. According to the Penal Code Act, mere penetration is sufficient to qualify as the sexual contact required for the crime of rape. The emphasis the courts place on providing proof of penetration to an allegation of rape is demonstrated by cases under the Penal Code Act. 2 The Criminal Code Act uses the term "*carnal knowledge*," which implies that the penetration of the vagina could be accomplished by the penetration of a foreign object, whereas the Penal Code Act uses the term "*sexual intercourse*," which implies that the penetration of the vagina could be accomplished by the penetration of a foreign object.

The Penal Code Act outlines what consent is not, but it does not define it. Even yet, it suffices to say that the victim's lack of permission is a necessary component of a rape accusation. 3 The consent cannot be obtained through coercion, deception, or fraud.⁶⁰ Aside from the many situations that the sections specify as to what would not constitute consent, it is interesting to note that even when a girl who is under 14 or of unsound mind consents, rape is still committed.⁶¹

Children under the age of 16 who have been sexually molested by individuals who hold positions of power are given special consideration in the Penal Code Act. Any consent given by a girl under the age of 16 to a teacher, guardian, or other individual tasked with her care or education is not considered legitimate consent, according to Section 283. In cases where the girl is between the ages of 14 and 16 and the consent is not given to her teacher, guardian, or any other person entrusted with her care, the prosecution will still need to demonstrate lack of consent.

The Penal Code Act does not make the same assumption that a boy under the age of 12 is unable to have carnal knowledge as the Criminal Code Act does. Therefore, if it can be demonstrated that the child has achieved the necessary maturity of understanding to determine the nature and effect

⁶⁰ Section 39(a) of the Penal Code Act

⁶¹ Section 39(b) and (c) of the Penal Code Act

of his act, there is nothing to prevent the prosecution from charging a child above 7 years of age, for example, with rape.⁶²

3.1.3 The Violence Against Persons Protection Act

So far, it appears that several legislative changes have elevated the crime of rape in Nigeria to its highest level ever. This is demonstrated by the National Assembly's enactment of the Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act 2015 (often referred to as the "VAPP Act"), which is limited to the Federal Capital Territory of Abuja. Many states in Nigeria have adopted their own VAPP Laws as a result of the innovations in the VAPP Act.

The VAPP-definition of rape is broader than the definitions given in the Criminal Code, Penal Code, and Sharia Penal Code. A person violates the law and is guilty of rape if:

(a) he/she purposefully penetrates another person's vagina, anus, or mouth with any other part of his/her body or anything else.

(b) the other person does not consent to the penetration, or (c) the consent is obtained through force, threat or intimidation of any kind, fear of harm, or false and fraudulent representation as to the nature of the act, or the use of any substance or addictive capable of taking away such person's will, or in the case of a married person, by impersonating his/her spouse/partner⁶³

As a result, the statute recognizes that a person can be raped through the vagina, anus, or mouth. An object can also be used to rape a person. The act also acknowledges men as victims of sexual crimes such as rape. Under the act, marital rape is also an offense. The Act also recognizes gang rape, which occurs when a group of people perform the act.⁶⁴ Rape convictions carry the possibility of life imprisonment.⁶⁵ If the perpetrator is under the age of fourteen, he or she faces a minimum of fourteen years in jail, and in all other situations, a minimum of twelve years in prison without the option of a fine.⁶⁶ In the case of gang rape, those convicted jointly or severally face a maximum sentence of twenty years in jail without the option of a fine.⁶⁷

⁶² Section 50 of the Penal Code Act.

⁶³ Part 1, section, 1(1), supra note 55

⁶⁴ Part 1, section 1(3), Ibid

⁶⁵ Part 1, section 1(2)

⁶⁶ Ibid

⁶⁷ Part 1, section 1(3)

The definition, penalty, and overall scope of rape and other sexual offenses have undergone significant positive modifications as a result of the provisions of the VAPP Act in Abuja and the VAPP Laws in several states of Nigeria. The following is a list of rape-related innovations:

- a) removing the restriction that states one spouse (husband/wife) cannot be accused of raping the other spouse (husband/wife) and expanding the definition of rape to include both sexes.
- b) Any person, male or female, has the potential to commit or be the victim of rape.
- c) expansion of rape-related offenses. Rape now includes any sexual assault through any hole in a human body. As a result, some behaviors that had previously only been sexual assaults, such as anal sex, oral sex, fingering, and even kissing.
- d) Increasing the severity of the rape penalty Unlike any other law in Nigeria, the VAPP Act and related statutes have established a 12-year minimum sentence for rapists. By doing this, the courts' (judges' and magistrates') discretion over the rapist's potential minimum sentence is removed. The maximum penalty for rape under other criminal statutes (the Penal Code and the Criminal Code) is life in prison; however, there is no minimum sentence. Therefore, this made it possible for courts and magistrates to impose very short prison terms on offenders, such as 5 years or even 3 years for rape. The VAPP Act, like other criminal laws, kept the death penalty as the ultimate punishment, although where the perpetrator is under the age of 14, the maximum.
- e) expansion of the body parts that can be raped as well as the objects that can be used to commit rape. A penis or any other thing, even a stick or a finger, can now be used as rape instruments. The human body's openings, such as the mouth, anus, and vagina, are now considered "rape-able" places.
- f) Gang rape has been taken into consideration, and each participant-rapist faces a 20-year prison sentence.

- g) As of right present, a court can mandate financial compensation for rape victims. The amount of reparation has no bearing on or lessens an offender's sentence or incarceration.
- h) For sexual offenders, there is now a Register. With this, anyone can look through such registers before hiring anyone to manage children and other soft targets of rape, including employers.⁶⁸

3.2 The problems/inadequacies of the law on rape/Societies View

Nigerian law's current rape-related laws are insufficient and antiquated; they must be updated to reflect the variety of scenarios in modern society that may qualify as rape. They are predicated on the idea that only a woman can be raped and are not gender neutral. Since a guy can only harm a female, Okagbue refers to this crime as "a gender focused crime."⁶⁹ His justification for this claim is based on the historical legal protection of male property⁷⁰, the ownership of a woman's body, and the reality that a man could decide when a woman became pregnant.⁷¹

With respect to these definitions of rape offered by the extant legislations, there are three fundamental problems that plagued these definitions and same will critically be antagonized by this researcher, and this include:

- i. Rape is not a gender-neutral crime;
- ii. it can only be classified as rape if the vagina is penetrated, not another bodily part.
- iii. There are various drawbacks to the law only classifying a penis's vaginal penetration as rape.

⁶⁸ Elombah D. (2009) The Black Race and Rape. Retrieved from [Hhttp://www.nigerianilagesquare.com](http://www.nigerianilagesquare.com)H accessed 02 November 2022

⁶⁹ Isabella Okagbue, *The Reform of Sexual Offences in Nigerian Criminal Law*, 2007, NIALS Press, p.4

⁷⁰ Ibid

⁷¹ Ibid

First off, the definition of the statute prioritizes women while neglecting male victims. The belief that only men can commit rape against women is enforced by the law. The historical protection of women as "property," either belonging to her father or her husband, can be linked to this position. The definition of the legislation emphasizes heterosexuality as well.⁷²

Sexual violence committed by a person of the same sexes cannot be described as rape because of the language's lack of gender neutrality⁷³. The outcome? As those who encounter this kind of assault have nowhere to turn to the law for help, it perpetuates the culture of silence. A more comprehensive definition of rape that expresses equal protection for all genders must be incorporated into Nigerian legislation.⁷⁴

This definition of rape also implies that it is not wide enough to guarantee the protection of other types of sexual violence that do not involve vaginal penetration. For instance, a woman's anus or mouth could be penetrated through penile penetration, and similarly, a woman's anus, mouth, or vagina could be penetrated by foreign objects or other bodies. Because of this, only sexual assault offenses under *section 360* of the *Criminal Code* are punishable by a prison term of two years, as opposed to rape, which is punishable by a life sentence.

The legislation ignores the possibility of penetration of a woman's mouth, anus, or vagina that is not consented to being just as traumatic and humiliating as penile invasion of the vagina. The law trivializes other types of sexual assault by doing this. The abhorrently low jail term and failure to categorize such actions as rape hinder women from pursuing legal recourse, which once again fosters the culture of silence.

*"Let the husband show his wife the affection she deserves, and let the wife show her husband the same. The husband has control over the wife's body; she has none. Likewise, the wife has control over the husband's body but the husband does not"*⁷⁵.

⁷² Esere M.O. & Idowu A.I. (2005) Causes and Consequences of Intimate Partner Rape/Violence *Nigerian Journal of Guidance and Counselling Vol 11 No 2*

⁷³ Omorodion H. & Olusanya (1998) The Social Context of Reported Rape in Benin City, Nigeria *Africa Journal of Reproductive Health 2 (2) 37 – 43*

⁷⁴ Onyejekwe C.J. (2008) Nigeria: The Dominance of Rape *Journal of Interactional Women's Studies Vol. 10*

⁷⁵ 1st Corinthians 7 ; 3 – 5 St Paul's Message to the Church in Corinth

The biblical passage mentioned above has historical and contemporary relevance to the subject of marital rape. This passage of scripture had a significant impact on English common law, which is still in use in commonwealth nations like Nigeria. There have been justifications for marital rape going back to the early 1600s. For instance, Sir Matthew Hale claimed in 1736 that marital rape is not considered to have occurred because the wife "*had handed up herself in this way unto her husband, which she cannot withdraw.*"

To preserve a woman's "honor" before her father or spouse, rape laws were created. These legislators and judges are more concerned with defending a man from the invasion of his female property than they are with safeguarding the bodily integrity of women. This theory is supported by customs involving the payment of the bride price, which hold that once the husband pays for the woman, the wife is his to keep. The Penal Code's Section 55, which permits the husband to physically punish his wife for "chastisement," also reflects the notion that the husband owns the woman.

Anyhow, the legal exception for marital rape is state-approved violence and harshness. It is allowed for males to have sex with their wives without their wives' consent and with impunity under certain circumstances. When a woman gets married, the law essentially says to dishonest men, "You can rape as much as you want, whenever you want."

It is evident from the foregoing that Nigeria's rape laws are unjust. However, the burden of proof for rape is significantly higher. The worst aspect is that the prosecution must establish beyond a reasonable doubt that the defendant did not really believe the victim was giving consent. Even if a defendant's justification for that notion is complete nonsense, he or she can nevertheless argue that he or she had a sincere belief that the victim was giving their consent. Therefore, there is no room for sexual compulsion or manipulation.

The Supreme Court ruled in *Posu v. The State*⁷⁶ stated that the prosecution must prove both the actus reus and the mens rea of rape beyond a reasonable doubt. Therefore, the prosecution must demonstrate that the accused engaged in non-consensual sexual activity with the victim that included vaginal penetration.

⁷⁶ (2020) LCN/4948 (SC)

In addition, they must demonstrate that the accused acted carelessly by not caring whether the victim gave her consent or that the accused meant to engage in sexual activity with the victim without getting her permission. Additionally, the Criminal Code Act of Nigeria still upholds the English case of *D.P.P v. Morgan*⁷⁷ (another out-of-date English piece of law). This burden is very onerous for the prosecution because it requires showing everything from the actual physical act of penetrative sex to the accused's state of mind. It leads to a lack of confidence in the legal system, which makes it harder for women to report rape.

According to **Section 211** of the *Evidence Act*, the defense may establish the woman's immoral character by questioning her during cross-examination about her relationships with other males, including the accused. According to Nigerian law, a woman's moral compass is located between her legs, this repulsive rule, which derives from an antiquated English common law rule, holds that the victim's sexual morality affects both the issue and the credibility of her witness. Because it is founded on the dangerous presumption that the victim must have given her consent at the time of the incident if she had previously given her assent to sex with the defendant or anybody else, this theory is patently stupid.

The fact that a rape trial can accept evidence of sexual history shows that Nigerian law thinks sexually active women are somehow less credible and incapable of being raped. This is quite backwards because the victim will only feel humiliated and distressed if the proof is admitted. Her sexual background has no bearing on the situation because rape is not sex but violence.⁷⁸

Another damaging deficiency on the Nigerian law of rape is the need for corroborative evidence. The term corroboration can be explained to mean the ratification, validation, verification, or confirmation of preexisting evidence by one or more additional independent witnesses.⁷⁹ Although it is trite law that a person may be found guilty based solely on the uncorroborated testimony of one witness, according to **section 200** of the *Evidence Act 2011*. Corroboration is thus not actually required to prove a criminal case. However, a review of rape cases in Nigeria reveals that judges need corroborative evidence before finding a defendant guilty

⁷⁷ Supra

⁷⁸ Onyemelukwe C. Legislating on Violence Against Women: A Critical Analysis of Nigeria 's Recent Violence Against Persons (Prohibition Act 2015). *DePaul Journal of Women, Gender & the Law*, 2016. 5(2).

⁷⁹ Oshiname FO, Ogunwale AO and Ajuwon AJ. Knowledge and perceptions of date rape among female undergraduates of a Nigerian university. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 2013: 17(3), 137-148

of rape. Cases like *IGP v. Sunmonu*⁸⁰ and *Iko v. State*⁸¹, among others, have established the validity of the need for corroboration before a guilty decision is rendered.⁸²

In *Iko v. State*⁸³, the judge plainly admitted that "*the corroboration requirement is merely practice in Nigeria; it has become a required practice, which is faithfully observed by judges*" despite the fact that it is solely a Nigerian legal requirement. One might wonder why Judges insist that others support a rape accusation in defiance of the Evidence Act.⁸⁴

Again, the need for corroboration may be traced back to English common law, which compelled judges to instruct juries that it would be dangerous to condemn based solely on the victim's uncorroborated account. This was done with the intention of shielding the defendant from unjust charges.⁸⁵

Since the dawn of time, males have argued that women are more likely to accuse men of rape because they are crazy, jealous, or ashamed of earlier sexual acts to which they gave their consent.⁸⁶ The need for verification, according to legal scholars and judges, will shield men from these women.

The requirement of a third party to corroborate a woman's account of rape raises the possibility that women are unreliable, highly emotional individuals whose word cannot be taken seriously unless it has been verified. Although it may be argued that false rape claims have risen over the years, but this is no stop gap to the societal view of sexualizing women and not believing them when they go through this gruesome nightmare, like the saying goes, "*one cannot throw away the*

⁸⁰ (2021) LCN/4962 (SC)

⁸¹ 2001 90 LRCN 2896

⁸² Odu B, Falana BA and Olotu O. Prevalence of Violent Sexual Assault on South West Nigeria Girls. *European Scientific Journal*, 2014, 10 (7): 471-481

⁸³ supra

⁸⁴ Awosusi AO and Ogundana CF. Culture of Silence and Wave of Sexual Violence in Nigeria. *AASCIT Journal of Education*; 2015, 1(3): 31-37.

⁸⁵ Ajuwon AJ, Olaleye A, Faromoku B and Ladipo O. *Sexual Behaviour and Experience of Sexual Coercion among Secondary School Students in Three States in North Eastern Nigeria*. BMC Public Health, 2006; 6, 310.

⁸⁶ Shaahu V, Ajuwon AJ, Onadeko MO and Lawoyin TA. Review of incidents of Rape from Police records in Ibadan, Nigeria, *African Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences*, 2004, 33: 275 – 278.

baby with the bathwater". Since rape frequently occurs in private by someone the victim knows and trusts, it is nearly impossible for the victim to find an impartial witness.⁸⁷

As a result, many victims decide not to disclose the incident because of this need. It is really terrible that the dignity and human rights of victims are suppressed in the legal system's attempt to defend the accused against unfounded accusations.⁸⁸ The corroboration rule will be eliminated, but this will not result in injustice being done to the defendant; rather, justice will be restored in this corrupted area of the law.⁸⁹

Much more troubling and shocking is the provision under the Sharia Penal Codes. In accordance with **Section 127** of the **Kano Sharia Penal Code Law**, proof of rape or Zina⁹⁰ (*extramarital sexual relations*) requires either a confession from the rapist or the support of four male witnesses.⁹¹ It is impossible to obtain a rape conviction due to the installation of these onerous conditions. Most rapes take place without the presence of witnesses. Therefore, finding just one witness would be challenging. But four male witnesses? It is not possible. The law has established an environment where rapists can act with impunity thanks to this divine mandate.⁹² Men can rape as many women as they like since they are aware that the victims will never be able to establish their innocence.

In conclusion, due to these regulations, there is now impunity throughout Nigeria's north. These rules merely act as a resource for guys who want to rape women without getting caught, not as a meaningful sort of protection.

⁸⁷ Ilonzo, N., Ndungu, N., Nthamburi, N., Ajema, C., Taejimeyer, M. and Theobald, S., 2009, 'Sexual Violence Legislation in Sub-Saharan Africa: The Need for Strengthened Medico-Legal Linkages', *Reproductive Health Matters*, Vol. 17 (34): 10-19.

⁸⁸ Peters, O. and Olowa, O., 2010, 'Causes and Incidence of Rape among Middle Aged and Young Adults in Lagos State, Nigeria', *Research Journal of Biological Sciences*, Vol. 5(10): 670-677.

⁸⁹ Imoukhuede, N., 2007, 'The Alarming Increase of Rape, gang rape and defilement in Nigeria', Women's Right Watch, Nigeria

⁹⁰ Azam H. *Rape as a variant of fornication (Zina) in Islamic Law: An examination of early Islamic legal reports*. Cambridge University Press; 2013

⁹¹ Shabbir M. *Outlines of Criminal Law and Justice in Islam*, p. 221

⁹² Onyejekwe, C., 2008, 'Nigeria: The Dominance of Rape', *Journal of International Women's Studies*, Vol. 10: 48-63.

CHAPTER FOUR

RAPE FROM THE VICTIM'S PERSPECTIVE

4.1. Introduction

Rape is a grave wrong, one too often ignored, mischaracterized, and legitimized. The offence is so vile that it warranted a judicial pronouncement in *Popoola v State* where the court held that it is heartless and one of the greatest offences that can be committed against any human. Consequently, laws and jurisdictions have been established to tackle the vice, including statutory changes and reenactments to meet recent societal and legal evolutions. Five modifications that have commonly reflected in the amended sexual offence legislations are lowered sentence structure, abolition of capital punishment as a sanction for rape, a graduated continuum of offenses and penalties, the reformulation of rape statutes to a gender-neutral definition of parties, and a change in terminology away from just rape to encompass such nomenclature as “criminal sexual conduct-to reflect defilement, sexual procurement and the likes. However, while the intent of the legal reforms was to reinforce justice and insure fairness, little attention has been given to the pertinent issue of addressing the unintended effect of these changes. That is, how some of the modifications, including systemized attitudes of the society, enforcement agencies and the judiciary, trivializes the offense of rape and devalues the victim. This chapter examines the impact of rape on rape victims from the victims’ perspectives in the light of how societal attitudes, judicial and police responses constitute victimization. This chapter focuses more on rape from the standpoint of women based on the understanding that although men can also be raped, but their victimhood accounts for a small percentage of rape. This is because; the culture of sexual violence is mostly perpetrated on women. Therefore, it would seem permissible to focus primarily on the experiences of women. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Violence against Women Survey, 82 percent of all juvenile victims of rape are female and 90% of adult rape victims are female⁹³. Similarly, the Nigerian Minister of Women Affairs and Social Development

⁹³National Institute of Justice & Centers for Disease Control & Prevention, Prevalence, Incidence and Consequences of Violence Against Women Survey (1998) <https://www.rainn.org/statistics/victims-sexual-violence> Accessed 13 November 2022

(FMWASD), Dame Pauline Tallen estimated at the 2019 International Day for the Elimination of Violence against Women that, about 2 million Nigerian girls experience sexual assault annually.⁹⁴

4.2. An Appraisal of the Victim's Traditional Perspectives on Rape

The legal history of rape is the history of male domination. Definitions of offense, evidence, legal defenses, and appropriate penalties were passed by males in accordance with traditional beliefs of propriety and the nature and characteristics of females. Over the years, two types of females were characteristically recognized by the society and the law-the chaste and the unchaste. According to Glacopassi and Wilkinson⁹⁵, the rape of a chaste female, if proved, brought forth the full force of the law⁹⁶; however, where the victim of the rape is an unchaste woman, the offense was often not punished but instead, translated into a public degradation stigmatization or ceremony of the “non-virtuous” female. This was buttressed by Macfarlane⁹⁷ when he said:

“In earlier times, the offence was linked more with notions of property and theft than with principles concerning the security of persons⁹⁸”

In Nigeria, accusations or testimonies of victims allegedly raped in certain perceived inappropriate locus in quos such as hotels, homes of their male invitees/alleged rapist, were undermined and often turned into morality and appropriateness hearings with targeted victimizations of the victim who according to the bulk of Nigerian “morality polices,” were not supposed to be in the rape scene in the first place the victims were blamed for rendering themselves vulnerable to rape and for their purported disregard of safety-an attitude that prioritizes location of offence over victim's travails.

In the light of this, a number of theorists have stated that this legal position was founded not simply of political inequality of females, but rather the fact of absolute inequality of females being considered less and the facts to the rape of a woman had to impute chastity or appropriateness of

⁹⁴ Solomon Vendega, 'The Law on the Offence of Rape in Nigeria; Challenges and Recommendations' <https://barristerng.com/the-law-on-the-offence-of-rape-in-nigeria-challenges-and-recommendations-by-ater-solomon-vendega/#>

⁹⁵ 'Rape and the Devalued Victim, Law and Human Behaviour' <https://www.deepdyve.com/lp/apa/rape-and-the-devalued-victim-Ph4K37Kyf6> Accessed 13 November 2022

⁹⁶ Uwaila

⁹⁷ MacFarlane Bruce, (1994) A Historical Development of the Offence of Rape.

⁹⁸ Ibid

the victim for the offense to be taken as a serious transgression.⁹⁹ Although recent trends in sexuality and sexual orientations has led to legal evolutions of rape which has resulted in a non-gendered definition of rape to include carnal knowledge of both males and females with any object, as seen in the Violence Against Peoples' Prohibition Act¹⁰⁰ which modified the gendered definition of rape under section 357 of the Criminal Code and section 282 of the Penal Code, the fact remains settled that females are hugely vulnerable to rape. And that, perceptions of masculine entitlements and dominance have an overwhelming bearing on both the rape culture and the societal and legal attitude accorded the offence and the victims...

Therefore, there is little doubt that through the legal system, the politically dominant male protected himself and all other members of his sex from all potentially unwarranted charges of rape, giving the accused advantages not seen as appropriate for those accused of any other crime. These advantages does not only protect the male from "unwarranted charges," but served to make it extremely difficult to convict of rape except in narrowly defined circumstances. In Nigeria, rape has become a trend as we hear of cases of sexual violence against children, women, and men. Only in 2007, the statistics of reported child rape cases showed 4035 victims Lagos, 1000 in Kwara State, 600 in Gombe State, 1200 in rivers state, 115 in Anambra State. In 2015, UNICEF reported that 1 in every 4 girls and 1 in 10 boys within and beyond Nigeria experience some form of sexual violence before the age of 18. Similarly, a community-based survey of rape estimated the rate at 1300 per 100,000 women a year; and with the advent of covid-19, coupled with the ongoing national crisis in Nigeria, a very distressing dimension of rape has increasingly gained prominence. According to human rights lawyer, Evans Ufeli, the count has recorded only 18% rape convictions, about 65 rape convictions between 1973-2009 in its legal history, and this has tripled by 2021 and 2022; not to mention the volume of unreported cases all because of the legal and societal difficulties surrounding the victims in the pursuance of justice.

These difficulties will be treated seriatim:

4.3. A Critique of the Legal and Judicial Hurdles of Proving Rape: The Victims Perspective

⁹⁹Schwendinger and Schwendiger, 1983; Brownmiller, 1975

¹⁰⁰ 2011. Section 3 of the Act defines rape as.....

Rape is arguably the most offensive kind of sexual assault known to man. It occupies this top spot amongst sexual assaults because it is not only an attack on the victim's body while it lasts, but like the stench of decomposed fish in a vehicle that lingers on even after evacuation, leaves the victim traumatized and rudely shaken for a very long time. As a matter fact, a good number of victims do not regain mental and psychological stability until their abusers are prosecuted and eventually convicted. However, In Nigeria, rape remains a controversial issue with a few victims reporting experiences because of the myriad of societal perception, prolonged steps in pursuing a case to logical conclusion of securing conviction, as well as psychological and physical residuals of the experience. Under this subheading, the attitude of the law- that is the enormous legal burden of proof placed on the poor victims-the judiciary and law enforcement agencies to rape victims will be considered in the light of the victim's perspectives and the impacts of the highlighted attitudes on them. And emphasis will be placed on child rape to dispel the law's excuse of presumption of innocence and motives of accusers.

The Legal hurdles of proving rape is found in legislations and defining sections or provisions, including the procedural standard of proof.

Section 357 of the Criminal Code¹⁰¹ provides thus:

“Any person who has unlawful carnal knowledge of a woman or girl, without her consent, or with her consent, if the consent is obtained by force or by means of threats or intimidation of any kind, or by fear of harm, or by means of false and fraudulent representation as to the nature of the act, or, in the case of a married woman, by impersonating her husband, is guilty of an offence which is called rape.”

By implication, for a charge of rape to succeed under this provision and its equivalents¹⁰², the prosecution must prove the elements of carnal knowledge or penetration, consent, capacity and additionally, corroboration; and the burden of proof required for proving these elements, is daunting. These elements will be examined billow:

4.3.1. Carnal Knowledge or Penetration

¹⁰¹Criminal Code, CAP “C38”

¹⁰² The Criminal Code, s.357; Penal Code, s.282; The Violence Against Peoples Prohibition Act, s.1; the Administration of Criminal Justice Act, Lagos State, s.258

This is the grave man of the offence of rape. Section 6¹⁰³ provides that the offence of rape is complete upon penetration. In other words, under this provision, rape is complete as soon as the male organ touches or enters the female vagina. For the offence of rape to be committed, there need not be the rupturing of neither hymen nor the emission of fluid; it has been held overtime that the slightest of penetration amounts to rape.¹⁰⁴ In *Julius v. State*¹⁰⁵ the court held that it is not enough that the prosecution/respondent said that the appellant had sexual intercourse with her without her consent, but the fact of penetration must be proved beyond reasonable doubt. The burden of proving penetration is often overwhelming on victims especially with respect to the decision in the landmark case of **Okoyomon v. State**¹⁰⁶ where the court held that a witness or third party must be close enough to ascertain whether there is actual penetration not merely that the defendant was caught on top of the complainant. Hence, it becomes a case of the complainant's words against the defendant's words as courts are reluctant to convict solely on the testimony of the accused.

In *Iko v. State*, the appellant, a taxi driver, was asked by the prosecutrix father to take her to school in his taxi cab. On their way, it was alleged that the appellant parked, wound up the glass, pounced on here and forcibly had sexual intercourse with her. He then dropped her to his apartment and drove away. It was around 9p.m. The prosecutrix ran out and reported to the appellant's neighbor who then called her bather and reported the incited. The father reported to the police, but the appellant denied raping the girl on arrest. He was convicted by the High Court and the conviction was confirmed by the Court of Appeal. But the Supreme Court quashed the conviction on the ground that the element of penetration was not sufficiently proved.

Furthermore, the definition of rape under the codes applies only to vaginal penetrations. It does not cover current trends of anal and oral rape. Although it can be argued that this hurdle has been mitigated by the modification in the Violence Against People's Prohibition Act (VAPP Act) which expounded the definition of penetration to all forms of penetration with any object; whether annually, orally or in any "opening in the body," including penile penetration, the said Act has regrettably been domesticated by no fewer than 18 states out of Nigeria's 36 states and the Federal

¹⁰³ Ibid

¹⁰⁴ R v. Madison; R v. Russen

¹⁰⁵ (2019) LPELR-48170 (CA)

¹⁰⁶ (1973) NSCC

Capital Territory, mostly southern states. The implication of this is that, the protective arms of the VAPP Act will not apply to victims of non-virginal rape in the states that have not domesticated it yet, leaving them with justice. As the position that “where there is law, there is remedy,” is not cast in stone.

Also, another important modification in the VAPP Act is the provision of compensation mechanism for the victims, which for the time in the Nigerian history of sexual offences recognized the victim’s need for financial compensation to cover for the costs of legal representation and other resources used in obtaining exhibits such as medical examinations, incurred by victims in the pursuance of the trial and furtherance of their entitlement to justice. However, the section failed to prescribe the compensations. It merely mentioned it.¹⁰⁷ More so, the concept of post penetration which is recognized in international criminal justice systems¹⁰⁸ is unfortunately still a foreign issue in Nigeria. This occurs where both parties initially consent to sexual intercourse, but one party withdraws consent during the act. The view in Nigeria is that since a machine cannot stop instantly on request, a man should not be expected to stop having sex once told to do so. This view is absurd as it fails to take into account the victim’s psychological state at the time, the recognition of her fundamental right to choice and her entitlement to justice in the criminal breach of same.

4.3.2. Consent

Traditionally, the law has defined the crime of forcible rape to be an act of sexual intercourse accomplished by a man with a woman not his wife, by force and against her will. The law on consent operates in four folds viz; sex without consent between a man and a woman, sex with force or if consent fraudulently obtained, sex while impersonating a woman’s husband and sex with any child whether male or female. The person must have capacity to consent, thus, a child or a person of unsound mind cannot give consent.

Section 260 of the Criminal Law of Lagos State, 2015¹⁰⁹ provides thus:

¹⁰⁷ Section 1(3) of the Act merely provided that the court shall also award appropriate compensation to victims as it may deem fit in the circumstance.

¹⁰⁸ *People v. John Z* (Cal.2003) 60 PP.183

¹⁰⁹ Operating only in Lagos State, but equivalent to the provisions in the Criminal Code and Penal Code

“Any man, who has unlawful sexual intercourse with a woman or girl without her consent, is guilty of the offense of rape.”

The issue of consent is a sensitive area and has always breed controversies. In DPP v. Morgan,¹¹⁰ the House of Lords stated that if the accused believed that there was consent, he should not be guilty, and that his believe does not have to be reasonable. This rule was criticized heavily and by 1976, the Sexual Amendment Act of Great Britain nullified the decision. However, the rule is seemingly still influencing the Nigeria rape adjudication system and the perspective of judges. This is because from the wording of the Nigerian statutes, there are reasons to believe that law is more focused on justifying offenders than protecting victims.

For child defilement cases, the law authoritatively provides that a minor cannot give consent. The Child Rights Act¹¹¹ is instructive to the effect that any person who shall have sexual intercourse with a child commits an offence of rape and is liable on conviction to imprisonment for life. It further provides that it is immaterial that (a) the offender believed the person to be a person of or above the age of eighteen years; or (b) the sexual intercourse was with the consent of the child.¹¹² Similarly, under the Criminal Code and Penal Code respectively, a person who has carnal knowledge of a girl under the age of 13 years or 16 years or indecently deals with a boy less than 14 years is guilty of a felony and is liable to prescribed punishments¹¹³. However, put a caveat to these sections by providing that it is a defense to a charge under the examined sections to prove that the accused person believed on reasonable ground that’s that the girl was of age.

The import of this clause and the bearing it has on the sexual orientation and safety of the vulnerable children and young persons who cannot give informed consent and who are left to the mercy people who are committed to taking advantage of children’s naivety. cannot be overemphasized. It is submitted that the exclusionary clause is a deliberate ploy by law makers to exclude incorrigible sexual predators, especially men in power or men of affluence who abuse

¹¹⁰ (1975)2ALL ER 347. In the case, Morgan invited three strangers to have sexual intercourse with his wife. He allegedly told them that that she was ‘kinky’ and was likely to struggle to get turned on. Morgan denied saying these. The three men violently had sexual intercourse with her and claimed, inter alia, that they believed Mrs. Morgan was consenting. They were convicted but not without the judicial blunders above.

¹¹¹ CRA, 2003, section 31&32. This Act was enacted as a federal law to protect the rights of children and is domesticated in most of the states in Nigeria

¹¹² Note that the provisions of the Child Rights Act are not restricted to any gender. It also recognizes that the offence can be committed by a man or woman.

¹¹³ Sections 215, 218 and 222 of the Criminal Code.

their power and financial status, to lure young persons into uninformed sexual intercourse. There is therefore little or no legal protection for this class of persons and they or their guardians cannot sustain justice against the offenders who will always rely on that proviso to excuse their criminal behavior and escape liability. This is because no such proviso reflected in the section that stipulated the offence of defilement.

Furthermore, in defining the element of consent, section 6 of the Criminal Code provides that unlawful carnal knowledge means carnal connection which takes place otherwise than between husband and wife. In other words, a man cannot rape his wife and the consent of a married victim during the subsistence of marriage, is irrelevant as her consent is continuing. This is a gendered provision which illustrates the protective power of the dominant male anchored on the culture that views women as properties. This exemption traces back to the 17th century when Sir Mathew Hale stated:

“The husband cannot be guilty of rape committed by himself upon his lawful wife, for by their mutual matrimonial consent and contract, the wife hath given up herself in this kind unto her husband, which she cannot retract.”¹¹⁴

Therefore, there is no legal protection for victims of marital rape except where the forcible penetration or violence occasioned grievous bodily injury. Additionally, in rape proceedings, evidence of the past sexual history of the victim could be used to discredit a female victim to demonstrate her poor moral character and impeach her claim of non-consent to the sexual intercourse, but the past histories (including past rape convictions of rape) is prohibited from being used as evidence, except where the offender puts his character in issue¹¹⁵. The law expects victims to resist to the utmost from the inception to the close of the attack to indicate resistance and no consent even though it has been held that consent derived from a victim's passivity resulting in weakness from weakness, is not consent. Thus, rape is the only crime that requires victim's active resistance up to the point of severe injury, as an indication of no consent. Also, there is a stereotype to the effect that delay in reporting a rape is a circumstance showing that the female gave consent, including the bias that a woman who had once consented to sexual intercourse was more likely to

¹¹⁴ Barry (1980:1088), Rape by the Devalued Victim.

¹¹⁵ See Section 180(g) of the Evidence Act, 2011 (on bad character and similar fact evidence)

consent again and that evidence of her “unchastity” reflected on her consent and credibility. This bias ridicules victims of intimate-partner rapes and discourages them from seeking justice.

4.3.3. Corroboration

Generally, corroboration is not an ingredient of the offence of rape, but has been adopted as a matter of practice in proving the offence. Pursuant to this, the courts have consistently held that it is not safe to convict on the uncorroborated testimony of the prosecutrix without caution. Consequently, supporting evidence such as eye witnesses, medical reports, incriminating struggle scenes must be adduced to connect the offender to the “alleged” rape. This becomes an issue where the victim is not availed with these resources to prove the rape accusation. Worst challenges are posed where a child is raped. This is because a child can only give unsworn evidence on behalf of the prosecution¹¹⁶ and pursuant to the provision of offences on defilement and other sexual offences of carnal knowledge perpetrated on children;¹¹⁷ such conviction cannot be secured on the uncorroborated testimony of the child.

The question of corroboration arose in the landmark case of *Isaac Sambo v State*;¹¹⁸ the appellant was alleged to have raped a 10 year old girl. The facts before the court were that the appellant asked the girl to help him get some water to take his bath. The girl brought the water and he asked the girl to bring the bucket into his room. Immediately she did do, he locked his room, increased his music set to the highest volume, pushed the girl unto the bed and forced his penis into her vagina. When the girl started to scream, he quickly withdrew, allowed the girl to dress up and pleaded with her saying “please don’t spoil my name” because he was a legal professional. He opened the door and allowed her to go. The girl went home, washed herself and reported the incidence to her brother who examined her and found traces of blood on her. She reported the case to the police, but medical examination never took place until two days afterwards. The court found the facts to be sufficient corroboration and convicted the accused. On appeal, the Supreme Court set aside the lower court’s judgment by stating as follows:

“All the facts presented before us in this case as corroboration are no more than circumstantial evidence and because a circumstantial evidence does not irresistibly; point to the appellant as

¹¹⁶ Evidence Act, 2011, section 209; *Meribe v Nweke*

¹¹⁷ Criminal Code Cap C38, sections 217, 218,219,221,222.

¹¹⁸ (1993)LCN/2527(SC)

having committed the offence of rape on the girl, the judgment of the high court on appeal is thereby set aside.”

The court also implied that in the absence of medical evidence the testimony of the girl’s brother (PW2) was not sufficient corroboration since he did not “witness the rape himself.” Similarly, in **Okoyomon v State**,¹¹⁹ two girls of 11 and 12 years respectively, were approached in the bush by the defendant who promised to take them to where they would fetch better firewood. He lured the younger one to a secret corner in the bush where he fell on her and forcibly inserted his penis in her vagina. When she was medically examined about 10 days after the incident, her hymen was torn and she was infected with a venereal disease. Medical evidence did not indicate how long her hymen had been torn and by whom or that the accused was also infected with the venereal disease of the same kind with that of the prosecutrix. The only corroborative in support of the prosecutrix was that of an eye witness who testified to walking in on them and seeing the accused on moving up and down on top of the girl. The carnal judge was doubtful as to whether the defendant attempted to have sex with the girl or had carnal knowledge of the girl. Nonetheless, he was convicted. However the Supreme Court quashed the conviction and held that;

- Penetration was not proved since the witness was not close enough to ascertain penetration
- Venereal disease was not sufficient because medical evidence failed to connect the disease to the defendant.
- Evidence of PW1 had limited probative value in terms of corroboration.

This decision imposes hearsay burden on the prosecution and the requirement that it is not enough for an eye witness to see the person locomoting on the victim-that he must be close enough to see if there was actual penetration, is absurd. The first instinct of a rapist on sighting a third party while in the act, is flight; requiring such proof therefore stretches into the place of impossibility.

Understandably, the basis of the corroboration rule is in the rule of numbers ‘which is that the more the number, the stronger the evidence. The common law rule is justified by the need to protect the accused person against unjust conviction, because human experience has shown that people can fabricate accusations to satisfy different motives, and alleged victims are no different kettles

¹¹⁹ Ibid

of fish. But this understanding ought not to in any way, trump the victim's right to the legal pronouncement and reinforcement of her fundamental right to safety and dignity. A balance must be created between the need to protect the innocent from false accusers and the need to accord justice to the victims of this heinous crime. In fact, on a mini-max pendulum, it has been stated that there is no evidence to suggest that most sexual assaults are false.

A report from both India and Britain, including Nigeria, showed that rape was the fastest growing crime in India with over 29, 000 incidences in 2011 and yet the rate of conviction for the offence was completely commensurate. The same incommensuration has been highlighted in Nigeria. In **Santhosh Moolya and Surendra Gowda v. State of India**¹²⁰, the Indian Supreme Court reasoned thus:

“Any statement of rape is an extremely humiliating experience for a woman, and until she is a victim of sex crime, she would not blame anyone but the real culprit. While appreciating the evidence of the prosecutrix, the courts must always keep in mind that no self-respecting woman would put her honor at stake by falsely alleging commission of rape on her, and therefore, a look for corroboration of her [clearly overwhelming] testimony, is unnecessary and uncalled for.”

According to Justice Sathasivam¹²¹,

“When a first information report is lodged by a lady with regard to the commission of offence like rape, many questions would obviously crop up for consideration before she finally decides to lodge the FIR. It is difficult to appreciate the plight of the victim who has been criminally assaulted in such manner. Obviously the prosecutrix must have also gone through great turmoil and only giving it a serious thought, must have decided to lodge the FIR.”

And what about the testimony of a child? Do children have motives to falsify or fabricate evidence, too? In **Francis Okpanefe v. State**,¹²² the appellant appealed against a decision of the appealed against a decision of the appeal court convicting him on a two count charge of rape and attempted rape. The complainant (PW1) was found by the learned trial to be a girl aged twelve years at the

¹²⁰ (2010) 5 SCC, India

¹²¹ Ibid

¹²² (1969) LCN/1643 SC

time of the alleged offences. She testified that the defendant called her and asked her to bring him water and when she did so, he pushed her into his room and forcibly had intercourse with her against her will. She did not report the incident to anyone. The defendant repeated the act a week later, but this time, it was so forcible that she couldn't walk properly which made her mother question her and she then told her mother what happened. The defendant had given her a shilling on the second occasion to assuage her tears. The mother (PW2) testified to finding the girl in a distressed position and to finding the shilling on her clothe when she examined her. Medical report showed rupture of the hymeneal ring confirming the fact of forcible penetration. The court held that the earlier complaint made to her mother, the money and the medical report and the fact that the appellant's plea of alibi failed, was not sufficient to amount to corroboration. This is a clear open-and-shut case of child defilement, yet the court refused to prioritize the plight of the victim.

This rule of corroboration portends an overwhelming challenge for prosecutors and rape victims of all sorts, not just children. This is because sexual abuse and violence occurs in private settings and thrives in the place of secrecy and in the absence of any third part to corroborate the evidence. In other words, in a majority of cases where the rapist was not caught in the act and not subjected to medical examination, there is usually no direct/circumstantial evidence that the defendant raped the child. Most times, the only evidence implicating the defendant in many rape cases is the victim's testimony which in the eyes of the law/courts holds no water. Consequently, the victim's pursuance of justice ends up thwarted and the rapist conversely validated.

In Nigeria, it is almost a crime to report rape. The criminal justice system seemingly scorns the brevity of the victims who report cases. Consequently, most parents or individuals choose to conceal sexual offences against their children or themselves to avoid being subjects of social stigma and scrutiny. For the few who are courageous enough to speak up, they face a failed criminal justice system that renders the double victims of both rape and a flawed bureaucratic process which considers their testimony as insufficient and unreliable.

4.3.4. Rape Culture and the Hurdle of Stigmatization

Rape culture is one of the most pervasive phenomena that cut across every stratum of society and life in general. It is Nigeria's most prevalent enabler of rape against women and men. It connotes the social environment that allows sexual violence to be normalized and justified. In Rape

culture remains remarkably persistent, regardless, and at the basis of much of the difficulties of addressing rape culture by administrative responsibility are the following:

According to psychologist Saul McLeod, social roles explain the part people play as members of a social group. He wrote that with each social group adopted, people's behavior get changed to fit the expectations been had on that role. Rape culture reinforcement is underpinned by the culture of victimization, stigmatization and ignorance. We see it constantly in the culture of masculinity that sees violence and dominance as "strong" and "male". That is the culture of patriarchal sexual entitlement. We also see it in the question-culture of "why did she visit him?", "why did she stay out late?" and in the statement-culture of "she was dressed like a slut. She was asking for it". And certain other stereotypes trailing victims. It is founded on certain other characteristics (both contextual and otherwise) which increases the vulnerability to sexual violence, of which sexual orientation is at its forefront. And in order to successfully end this, the following social roles must be employed.

According to the United Nation's Feminist Movement, rape culture is pervasive. It is embedded in the way we think, speak, and move in the world. It manifests itself in our sexual attitudes. This pervasive culture can be both individually and collectively corrected through sexual education or sensitization. In Nigeria, there is an imbalance of sexual orientation whereby the language of safety is only impacted in the girl child-to dress decently, to avoid acting in inviting manners, etc, with the males lacking in the understanding of consent. Social role will equally address this through education and sensitization.

4.3.5. Judicial Hurdles: Courtroom Observations of Judges Demeanors to Victims

What do judges do with their authority in rape prosecutions and victim examinations, after reading and hearing victim's (especially women's) testimony about sexual violence? Do judges express irritation, impatience, judgmental attitudes and even hostility toward rape victims in courtrooms? Or do judges use their authority to express concern for victim's safety and connect them with resources that can protect and empower them?

From court to court and judge to judge, dramatic differences exist in the way that raped victims are treated. These differences are so well understood by volunteer advocates that victims are at times forced to avoid certain courts and particular judges or even to come back another day in the

hopes that someone else will be presiding over the hearings. In fact, in extreme situations of courtroom subtle backlashes and indifference, some victims withdraw from the proceedings.

In his instructive essay, „Judicial demeanor is best understood as the emotional presentation of authority by judges. The focus on demeanor as *emotional presentation* frames judging as “emotional labor.” Judges intend to have an emotional impact on victims and defendants, and the Judicial Code of Conduct addresses this responsibility. The kind of emotional impact judges have and the way that they accomplish this are the central to the question of demeanor. The emphasis on authority derives from the fact that in courtroom, the weight of the institutionalized power imbalances every interaction and names the manner in which judges “do authority” in the courtroom particularly in setting where those authorities is needed for the purpose of reinforcing the victim’s right to human dignity and safety.

Consider the case of a judge who ordered. A woman out of the courtroom for wearing sleeveless dress. The woman appeared for her cross-examination, but before even examining her case the male judge determined that she was inadequately deferential to the court in her appearance.

“Ma’am, I’m sorry, I won’t be able to hear this case, not the way you are dressed. This is a courtroom. You don’t come in hugging sleeveless gown to a courtroom. That is why you people get raped. This was not an emergency. You need to go and change and come back in the appropriate attire”¹²³

The question of judicial demeanor was the crux of the public scandal involving Judges Heffernan, King and Tempone in 1986¹²⁴ where..... In Nigeria, Judicial demeanor played an important role in victim’s experiences in with rape prosecutions. It is already apparent that being in court in it was for many victims a memorable, even traumatic experience and in some cases, judges’ responses amounted to a secondary victimization. To this effect, Stark and Anne have argued that rape consists of “dual trauma,” the result of not just violence but social entrapment arising from institutional collusion and indifference. In their words;

“the modal experience of rape is a dual trauma, fear, anger and a fundamental feeling of a loss of sense of self induced by the offender’s subjugation combined with a sense of increasing

¹²³ An Anambra High Court Judge to a rape victim

¹²⁴

entrapment....Typically, [this] sense of entrapment is a reality-based response to a history of denial, minimization, and victim blaming by those from they have sought support and protection, including police and the custodians of courtrooms.¹²⁵”

There is a deep mistrust in the judiciary whereby judicial officers view rape accusations with a needle’s eye. This is indicated by the necessity for a corroborating witness, the resistance requirements and the ability to examine the sexual history of the victim in great detail. Demming and Eppy posited that one of the consequences of common law rape statutes is that they shift the focus of attention from the offender to the victim. As a result, rape victims have commonly complained that the judicial demeanors made them feel as if they were the ones on trial; as if they were responsible for the rape because of how they acted or that they did not resist strongly enough. In fact, it was observed in cases in which there were no aggravating circumstances, judges tended to be more critical of victims and inferred that the victim placed herself in a hazardous situation and should take the blame for the consequences. Questionable circumstances that lead judges to this assumption of risk are varied, ranging from inappropriate dressings and locations of victims to drinking. One commentator wrote:

“A woman with an acceptable reason for being out alone at night is attacked with a weapon by a stranger who leaves her unconscious in an alley. But change many of the fact-remove the weep [on and the injury, make the woman a prostitute or the man her husband or someone she met in a bar-and the argument weakens.¹²⁶”

In other words, many aspects of our judicial culture conspire to deny rape victims benefits of the victim role by denying the legitimacy of her claim. It is not surprising that the treatment of the rape victim in the arms of the law became a feminist issue demonstrating the destructiveness of discriminatory treatment of women.

4.3.6. Administrative Hurdles: The Attitude of the Police

One of the greatest challenges of rape victims in Nigeria is the discouragement and victim blaming received from officers of the law, such as the police. It is common knowledge that the police are the first bus stop in the administration of criminal justice-the report, the arrest, arraignment,

¹²⁵

¹²⁶ Hotchkill (1978:29)

investigation constitutes the preliminary stages before prosecution; and the appalling abundance of police extortion of victims in the guise of investigation is a huge turn-off to victims. Most victims choose not to report cases to the authorities as a result of this. BBC news, Lagos referring to this barricade on the 4th of June 2020, described Nigeria as a “tough place to convict a rapist”, and because the purpose of law is to serve as a deterrent to offenders, justice gets ultimately defeated thereby driving on looking victims into silence (which in turn promotes rape culture) The prevalence of rape culture is predicated upon the ineffectiveness of the police, as those brave enough to report are not just extorted, but also targeted with derogatory comments at the police station. Recently, an Assistant Superintendent of Police was reportedly demoted for his notoriety in fingering rape victims, especially children, in a bid to ascertain the truth value of their claim through the tightness or looseness of their vagina.¹²⁷

Many survivors do not trust the police because they have witnessed their culture of stigmatization and victim-ridicule, and seen in allegations that are improperly investigated. For example, in a recent study of 155 rape allegations reported to police in Anambra state, only 12 were investigated, and none resulted in convictions¹²⁸

¹²⁷ Sahara Reporters ‘Nigerian Assistant Police Superintendent, Vincent Accused of Sexually Assaulting Teenage Girl Detained in Enugu Cell for 5 Days’ <https://saharareporters.com/2022/09/02/nigerian-assistant-police-superintendent-vincent-accused-sexually-assaulting-teenage> Accessed 13 November 2022

¹²⁸ Oludayo and Oluchukwu:’ Characterizing Rapists and Their Victims in Select Nigerian Newspapers.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION

5.1 Summary of Findings

The aim of law in the society is noted to be tied to its function in the society which are; law as a regulatory order, as an instrument of social change and as intervening instrument of social justice. Consequently direct justification and foundation is created for the intervention of law in rebalancing the negative effect of effects of the indirect protection of rapists under the law on rape victims in both the social environment and the criminal justice proceedings in Nigeria. Making a case for the modification of enabling rape legislations of the country and the states therein requires a critique of the legal frameworks using the doctrinal theory. Thus, it is of great importance to introduce the devalued victim's perspective which is central concern to analyzing their fundamental right to redress and justice, especially the adjudicatory system in order to explain the ways in which the law has been instrumental to the disregard and stigmatization of rape victims (who are mostly victims).

The crime of rape has been legislatively transformed in our society through statutory redefinition, changes in terminology, and changes in punishment as well as changes in the extralegal processing of the victim. Many of these changes were instituted for pragmatic reasons that reflect desirable goals, such as streamlining the processing of offenders and increasing the certainty of punishment, including the provision for compensation¹²⁹. However, While many of these changes have undoubtedly served the interest of the victims (rape shield laws, more humane processing by the criminal justice system, gender neutral definition of rape), a number of the legal reforms have done the victims a disservice by either ignoring the offence,¹³⁰ trivializing the offence¹³¹ and/or devaluing the victim's experience.

This long essay uses the humanitarian legal theory and critical discourse analysis approach in providing a victim perspective on the Nigerian extant laws on rape and sexual offences/assault. Equally noteworthy is the influence of patriarchy and customary practices on how rape victims are

¹²⁹ As incorporated in the Violence Against People Prohibition Act, section 1

perceived, especially girls and women. This long essay deduces that the jurisprudence of laws in Nigeria derogate and marginalize rape victims, contributing by extension, to the impairment of their ability to prosecute rape offenders and access the justice system. This in effect infringes their human right. Accordingly, if the purpose of the law is to attain justice and the same law provides for rules and principles which are adverse to the notion of justice. It suffices to say that the purpose of law is defeated. Human right issues are equally social justice issues. The stigmatizing laws and highhanded regulations on admissibility of victim testimonies affect the actualization of remedy in light of the notion of “ibi jus ibi remedium” which the justice system is founded on. To remedy this lacuna, a legal environment that encourages victims in seeking justice, is required.

5.2 Observations

Despite the protections afforded in the extant statutes in Nigeria, rape culture remains pervasive, rape is still committed in marriage beds and rape victims, especially women, are largely undervalued and stigmatized even by custodians of the law. There is no denying the widespread and systemic maltreatment meted on rape victims from the point of disclosure/.report to the police and the society to that of facing demoralizing judicial demeanors in hearings, which often reflects in rulings.

The point is that law has a “socio-pedagogic” and a “secondary social control” function. The law instructs the populace by defining socially unacceptable acts and, through sanctions, ranks these acts as to their degree of acceptability. The rape legislations and the attitude of enforcement officers embody a compromise that in effect transforms rape from a heinous crime that shocks the public, to a disreputable act that necessitates a lower level of punishment or no punishment at all. Therefore, it is submitted that law affords no protection unless it is enforced. Feminist legal critics have argued that laws that exist on paper are frequently ignored, particularly when they apply to women (victims) and contradict social customs, beliefs and rape cultures and biases. An additional concern is that formal acceptance of treaties may mask failures to implement legal provisions and requirements. Consequently, it would result to the inclusion of victim’s perspectives and considerations of their unique challenges in pursuing justice and reinforces their right to safety and human dignity.

5.3 Recommendations

In order to ensure systemic change in the rape culture, the following is recommended for due consideration and possible implementation:

- It is pertinent to modify certain provisions of the statutes on sexual assault, whether as of law or practice, including the incorporation and redefinition of a legal system that takes into account the personhood of the victim and acknowledges the victim's experience.
- Special courts should be created to hear cases involving rape and other similar offences while providing the victims with the privacy they require. This is because Nigeria embodies a society that is unaccommodating and unreceptive to rape victims based on stringent cultural and religious beliefs. This makes it difficult, almost impossible for rape victims to testify in open court and prove their case, as they have to deal with the judgmental biases and inferences of the court of public opinion. Also, it is to be remembered that our High Courts are already encumbered with a lot of cases and litigation is ordinarily, not fast and expedient. Sometimes, the victims decide to drop their charges rather than testify in court because they are unable to deal with repeated adjournments and lingering hearings, including the number of persons they have to face in the open court. Justice delayed is justice denied. Where a special court is provided, the identity of the victims can be protected, which in most cases are young girls, as only interested parties will participate in the court proceeding.
- The requirement of corroboration in the Evidence Act should be amended to relax the burden of proof required in proving rape. The burden of proof required in sustaining a rape conviction in Nigeria is daunting on rape victims as it puts the victims on trial in lieu of the rapist. The use of compelling circumstantial evidence should be adopted to replace the requirement of corroboration, especially in defilement cases involving innocent children who have no motive to fabricate testimonies. This is because rape is typically committed in secret and out of the public eye. The possibility of a third party is almost always highly improbable. And requiring difficult corroboratory evidence as enumerated in *Okoyomo v State* (supra) discourages victims from prosecuting offenders.
- Stiffer penalties should be given to rape offenders there is need to pass laws that do not trivialize sexual offences like the classification of child defilement as a misdemeanor in the

Codes. The present laws appear lenient and lack the force of deterrence. Moreso, the discretion granted to judges to reduce maximum sentences has frequently led to ridiculous punishments and sentences as seen in *Musa v State* (supra), thus the need for definitive provisions of punishments.

- We have seen that the stigmatizing undertone of the police, ranging from victim-blaming to the imputations of dishonesty in the victim's testimony or report. Nigerian police station's reporting system leaves a lot to be desired. Police officers are often hostile and un-empathic to victims. It is suggested that Police be trained to treat rape reports professionally, and they should learn to wear a human face while corresponding with victims. This will guarantee that the victims receive the respect and emotional support they need from the personnel in charge of the investigation and prosecution in court.
- In the adjudicatory process, the courts should always advert their minds to the hardship occasioned by the burden of prove resting on the victim. They should do everything to see that they are not hindered in any way from making their case by any biased or flimsy excuses which will lead to unjust acquittal of a sex offender to the detriment of justice and the poor victims. Most importantly, the attitude of courts to victims has a strong bearing on the victim's post-sense-of-self and his or her perception of justice. Therefore, judges should use their authority to ensure that the victim's sense of dignity and safety is reinforced.
- Our Criminal and Penal Codes are replete with provisions which enable excuses sexual offenders, such as exculpatory proviso to the consent principle-which allows child defilement offenders to rely on and be excused by the defence of reasonable belief of age. We recommend amendment of such provisions to purge our laws of such unbecoming, enabling provisions.
- The presumption of innocence principle can be distracting when applied un-judiciously. Thus, a balance should be drawn between the prioritization of the principle and that of ensuring the actualization of justice.

- Marital rape should be criminalized. Provisions to the effect that a man cannot rape his wife is an affront to the tenets of human right and infringes a married woman's fundamental right to the freedom of choice, including her right to sexual reproductive health and safety.

The acknowledgement of victims' perspective in the statutes is not only a demand for simple justice but can also be seen as a necessary condition for protecting their psychological well-being and reinforcing their personhood and dignity. Without the active participation of the key actors in our criminal justice system, the purpose of law as a tool for achieving law and order and actualizing justice, will not be achieved. Therefore, the lacunas in our laws should be addressed.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

This long essay in analyzing the indirect protection of rapists under the Nigerian law, established the fundamental objectives of law in the society, appraised the challenges of rape victims in pursuing justice from their own perspective, and gave an in-depth criticisms of the extant, enabling laws. Finally, it established the prospects of the laws as instruments of justice and victim vindication.

5.5 Suggested Areas of Research

Provisions are not exhaustive of rape enabling laws and cultures in Nigeria, and this affords one an area of further research: Social stigmatization, impact of poverty and the feminization of poverty, rigid enabling patriarchal, moral and customary beliefs, the role of religion and continued widespread violence against women, have further increased the indirect protection of rapists and the undervaluing of victims. Consequently, as an extension, a research into these areas is suggested.

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